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Project Title

**Automatic Control Tools with Applications
to Gas and Wind Turbines for Fault
Monitoring**

Abstract

Gas and wind turbines play a major role within industrial and energy industries. However, anomalies of faults regularly occur, which can cause functional impact within the gas turbine and beyond. This report describes research studies on condition monitoring/fault detection methods used throughout the industry with application to gas and wind turbines. These are best described under four common fault scenarios that occur regularly within wind and gas turbines. These common faults are replicated within a MATLAB/Simulink simulation provided by the former ABB Alstom (Lincoln, UK) and kk-electronic (Ikast, Denmark, Prof. Peter Fogh Odgaard). On the other hand, real-time data from wind turbines were provided by the Ming Yang Smart Energy Group Ltd. (Zhongshan, Cina) through projects with the University of Sheffield (Sheffield, UK) and Beijing Normal University (Beijing, China). The simulations enable a comparison of fault effects to be made, based on initial conditions and fault levels. It is interesting to study the effects of each fault on the simulated gas and wind turbine operation. The report discusses how the gas and wind turbine condition monitoring task can be achieved via several methods, focusing on the most suitable choices of methods and important factors such as cost and system offline time. A technique known as Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA) can also be used, especially for gas turbines, to determine how critical an individual fault can be. The study discusses how different tools can be used to determine the best-suited operation and maintenance technique for a gas turbine. Alongside the description of typical gas and wind turbine faults, their effects on engine systems and wind turbine components are also described as in the latter case safety-critical issues that must be addressed and in which system downtime cannot be considered. Further final application examples focusing on automatic control tools applied to wind turbines are also presented. A brief introduction to neural networks, artificial intelligence and adaptive tools is also included in this report.

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1.0 Introduction to Gas Turbines

Fault finding and diagnosis of gas turbines are a vital way of monitoring a system's health; when operational, the data found within the results can be used to predict trends (Tahan,2017), which in time can be used to ensure a reliable operation and maintenance plan, helping to improve the efficiency of operation. Gas turbines can be seen as rotating machinery, as can generators, compressors, and pumps, which all fail due to harsh conditions when operating. The aviation field is the highest field where failure occurs within gas turbines (Salilew et al. 2021). This then leads to high economic losses, which can be as high as 60% of the routine maintenance cost of aircraft (Salilew et al. 2021). This is the reason for condition monitoring of the system, as, in time, the trend prediction can reduce the cost of maintenance of all rotating machinery within a system.

Gas turbines comprise the turbine, combustor, and compressor, which can be shown schematically in Figure 1; these generic turbines are used widely throughout industry, power plants, aerospace jet engines, and ship engines (Salilew et al. 2021). Typically, Gas turbine's operational conditions are high-temperature, high-speed, and high-stress environments, causing a harsh operation, which can lead to performance deterioration. This can be a fault of a part within the turbine or a defect within the instrumentation, which will be monitoring numerous parts within a turbine. Sensor faults can be detected by adaptive mode observing, which can detect uncertainties within the monitoring of the system (Chapman et. al 2016). Adaptive monitoring can also extract the noise from underlying measurements associated with the system, which can discriminate between faults, thus controlling fuel signals, turbine

axial speed, and exhaust temperature, which are requirements within the system, which is subject to disturbance.

Figure 1: Schematic of a gas turbine (Hossain, 2019).

Harsh gas turbine operating conditions lead to components interfering with instrumentation which monitors vibration and thermodynamic parameters. This in turn can lead to uncertainty or reduced accuracy of diagnosis of a fault within the system. Hence ‘transferred learning’ can be a great tool as it compares data from two turbines to learn and output knowledgeable data, allowing a comparison for trends.

The Brayton cycle, as the thermodynamic system on which the gas turbine cycle is based uses air as a medium of fluid to be combusted within the system once compressed. The combustion results in the production of power from the turbine (Ahmed, 2009). This cycle consists of adiabatic and isentropic compression of gas, after applying heat at constant pressure, and the energy extraction comes about from gaseous expansion (Chapman et.al 2016). This can be shown below in a schematic of the Brayton cycle.

Figure 2: Brayton cycle schematic (Connor, 2019).

Within this project, a simulation of an Alstom gas turbine with three initial conditions and four faults is used. These are common faults associated with gas turbines in the power and aeronautical sectors, the data will be compared with real-life case studies around gas turbines allowing an understanding of what malfunctions and failures can occur if gas turbines are left to continue operating with marginal errors (i.e. leading to more serious faults), Marginal errors are also labelled as faults that can be difficult to detect or are “incipient faults” if left unrecognized or detected. Along with studying the errors and failures or faults, the importance of instrumentation within the system to monitor individual parts will be investigated as to why this is such a curtailed part of the system.

Gas turbines should be monitored through condition monitoring (or fault detection) throughout the design, operations, and maintenance through to decommissioning to understand trends made within the errors of a system. This practice improves the change of

the turbine remains operational with minimal. Downtime can be costly if not planned e.g. through a predictive maintenance schedule. FMEA can be an important tool when providing a plan within the design through to the decommissioning of a system, FMEA is used widely throughout engineering as it is deemed to be a lean way of working, along with implementing sections of likelihood within the upkeep of a system (Iqbal, 2018)

Numerous fault detection methods have been used to monitor gas turbines, performance-based monitoring being the preferred method through industries, as this advanced method is deemed to be the most cost-effective method to investigate engine performance and degradation of the system. Performance-based monitoring allows a quick and dependable comparison of data within a gas turbine which can be dependable for companies to refine operations and maintenance techniques (Barad, 2012). Turbine and compressors are highly critical within a gas turbine system. The performance of a combustion chamber is determined by the degradation of the system and cannot be detected using methods such as gas path analysis. To conduct a condition monitoring health assessment on a system using diagnostics, operating parameters should be known, in the simulation used within these reports, all parameters are known and allow the data to be measured and compared.

Figure 3 shows a comparison of data-driven methods and model-based methods for fault finding within a system, Data driven methods determine error due to knowledge and training of trends within a system by collecting data from feedback of output data within the system operation, However, model-based monitoring requires a model of the system and mathematical data of how the system should work to follow inconsistency within the systems operations.

Figure 3: Data-driven VS model-based diagnosis (Bechini, 2010).

Throughout this project, critical analysis of the different conditioning monitoring methods, along with simulation of faults within a gas turbine system will allow an in-depth discussion as to which methods should be used within gas turbine systems. Comparison of realistic faults

within systems will allow a 'best suited' method for the operation and maintenance of gas turbine systems which allows the system to remain in service for as long as possible. It is also necessary from the study to understand how to interchange within the system before failure can occur which can cause catastrophic failure within the turbine. So, a form of redundancy, either repeated hardware or analytical redundancy, should be used for areas of the turbine where faults are more likely.

1.1 Project Research on Gas Turbines

Using research through literature to understand gas turbines, how they work and common faults within the system and how these can be monitored throughout service can be implemented in the following steps. (Djeddi, et al., 2021).

1. Research gas turbines and the workings of the system.
2. Condition monitoring methods used to detect faults within the systems.
3. Importance of planned maintenance of a system.
4. Simulation of common faults within the Alstom simulation.
5. Critically analyze methods which can be best suited to gas turbine and jet engine maintenance plans to avoid high cost and downtime.

Once these initial steps have been made and a good foundation of knowledge has been obtained the simulation should then compare faults with initial conditions and the explanation of how the faults effect the system performance and if left untreated how they can affect the system's life cycle.

2.0 Considerations on Gas Turbines

The project fault finding of a gas turbine is solely a research and IT-based project using data freely available on the internet, along with software provided by Prof. Ron Patton, therefore all input will be used throughout and will be freely available making all ethical considerations negligible for the whole project.

Software for this project has been downloaded through the university and throughout the project Simulink and MATLAB have been used for academic use only.

All information used within this project has been an interpretation of other works within the literature review and this will be reflected when concluding the report, the conclusion and discussion for this project will be concise and written in a way that all personnel reading this report can understand the findings and outcome of the project clearly, however, the outcome of the project could contain error, therefore this project should be used purely for the backup of other findings and not to be used as an isolated report when studying fault finding and condition monitoring of gas and wind turbines.

3.0 Literature Review on Gas Turbines

3.1 System model and components

Gas turbines consist of complex parts which create the overall assembly which can be categorised into sections of the turbine, these can be seen schematically in Figure 4 below

Figure 4: schematic of a gas turbine parts (Ocando, 2020).

The simple schematic of Fig. 4 shows airflow direction as blue arrows. This takes the air through the air intake, through the compression vane, which compresses the air into a high-velocity gas which is injected into the combustion chamber, along with the flow of fuel. The combustion process produces a higher velocity gas through heat and injects the combination into the turbine blades, allowing the turbine to create energy needed to allow the turbine power to be used for either electricity within a power plant or, acceleration for aeronautical applications (jet engines), excess energy is then released through the exhaust system.

This simple explanation shows the workings of the gas turbine itself, However, the workings of a turbine are much more complex than this thus the knowledge of each part of the turbine is crucial within the monitoring a gas turbine.

The gas turbine consists of 3 major parts. (MAX, 2022)

- **The compressor**, whose role within the system is to draw air into the engine, through the vanes pressurizes, and feeds the air into the next stage, the combustion chamber through speeds as high as hundreds of miles per hour.
- **The combustion system**, this part can be made up of rings of fuel injectors that inject fuel into combustion chambers through a steady flow monitored via the valve angle where the air mixes. The mixture is burned at temperatures over 1010 degrees C. The combustion produces a high-temperature gas which streams and expands through the turbine section through having a high gas velocity gas stream.
- **The turbine** is a complicated array of alternate stationary and rotating vanes. while hot

gas combusts and expands throughout the turbine, the rotating blades accelerate. The rotating blades perform functions of a dual nature: they drive the compressor to draw more pressurized air into the combustion section and produce the force which spins the generator to produce energy output of the system, any excess energy is then vented out through the exhaust system.

Jet engines used within the aeronautical industry are much lighter in weight than their industrial turbine counterparts. Strictly speaking, the jet engine is not a gas turbine, The source of fuel is not gas; however, they are designed for mixing fuel along with air which ignites and produces the desired output for thrust when energy is released through the exhaust. Like the industrial gas turbine, the system components are the same however the use of hot air through the exhaust is the energy needed for propulsion. This is in contrast to the industrial gas turbine, in which the rotation of the turbine blade is the important energy output (i.e. driving a shaft). Along with the different energy uses a jet engine weighs less than its industrial gas turbine counterpart, with much smaller assembly. However, the jet engine requires much more instrumentation as catastrophic failures within a jet engine can have a high impact because of its safety-critical requirements. For a jet engine downtime is not a practical consideration, hence the instrumentation used within the system is changed much more frequently to that of an industrial turbine due to the system needing a much higher safety factor.

3.2 Performance of Gas Turbines

Gas turbines' performance starts to deteriorate with issues regarding the system's components; common faults occur such as turbine ageing, compressor contamination, altering ambient conditions, and fouling of parts due to mechanical setup. For these performance deteriorations to be limited, critical qualities within the system must be made. These are mechanical aids within the design of the turbine, such as altering the power turbine, compressor inlet guides, and nozzle valve guides. (Sanaye, 2020). Along with these simple mechanical adaptations within the turbine, the efficiency can also be increased through process engineering by additional components to allow tasks such as compressor intercooling, this allows the air to be tightly compact due to keeping the temperature of the compressed air down while compressing, turbine reheat this is involved within the exhaust system, and water injection to aid with the combustion of fuels (Ahmad, 2009)

3.3 Degradation

Deterioration of a gas turbine and jet engines happens in many factors. However, above all other aspects, two main categories occur within the cause of problems. These are performance-related issues such as compressor contamination, seal damage, instrumentation failures, and inconsistent combustion (Sanaye, 2020). Some of these failures can be replicated within the simulation used in this report. They can show just how problematic they can be to the system. The second category in which a gas turbine can deteriorate would be many mechanical issues, which can happen due to human error within the installation of the gas turbine but can also be problematic due to the harsh conditions in

which the system works. These conditions can affect the mechanical soundness of the system to change. These failures are problems such as misalignment when coupling the components of the system, causing unbalanced rotation, insufficient oil lubrication, and bearing failure (Salilew et al. 2021). All these failures within the system can impact the other components within the system.

3.4 Condition Monitoring

Condition monitoring of a gas turbine and Jet engine can be performed in many ways. The main application process of condition monitoring can be shown in Figure 5, which utilizes data to check the severity of the problem, which is used to create an operations and maintenance plan for the system. Not only is this beneficial to understand the systems trends and knowledge of problems that can occur, but this also helps to reduce operations costs due to planned maintenance for specific parts of the system before they cause catastrophic problems, which in turn minimizes downtime for the system thus reducing operations cost, minimising fuel consumption (Bechini, 2010) but also extends the life and overall safety of the gas turbine.

Figure 5: Condition monitoring, prognosis, and health management (Vachtsevanos, 2016).

There are two monitoring categories when condition monitoring a system, which is classified as non-linear and linear (Kamboukos, 2005). Linear monitoring methods have a higher degree of accuracy when estimating the deterioration of the performance of a system. Model-based monitoring has both linear and non-linear aspects combined, this can be problematic in carrying out tasks, and non-linear methods only are referred to as data-driven. Therefore, specific fault-finding methods are used depending on the outcome that is needed. Table 1 shows the different methods assigned to each category.

Table 1: Performance-based categories (Salilew, et al. 2021).

Data-driven method	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Hybrid AI Methods• Artificial neural network (ANN)• Deep transferred learning
Model-based method	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• gas-path analysis (LGPA)• Kalman Filter (LKF)• Least Squares (LWLS)

Model-based condition monitoring techniques are flexible because they can detect unanticipated faults within the system by using linear and nonlinear data to predict errors (Kong, 2014). Although flexibility within the methods of obtaining data through this data, model-based methods cannot ideally monitor noise and vibration problems accurately, unlike data-driven methods, which, though learning as a human brain, would these methods allow accuracy when implemented (Li, 2002). A method such as an artificial neural network (ANN) can develop a model analytically. The model will be updated throughout the gas turbine service, and the data will adapt to the system's actual performance, learning trends, and patterns of error throughout the parameters output within the data. This data is checked along with ordinary data for the system can execute performance-based monitoring (Tahan et al., 2017).

Model-based methods as used within the simulation of this project engage with the performance of the system by being dependent on parameters such as fuel mass flow, temperatures of specific locations, output performance, the efficiency of the components, which are all calculated mathematically within the software (Fentaye et al., 2016).

Data-driven methods can detect faults than can be anticipated within a system's performance. However, research on fault-finding within industry systems is more focused on a hybrid cycle of multiple data-driven methods due to the advantages and disadvantages of each method (Romesis et al., 2014).

3.5 Data-Driven Methods

3.5.1 Artificial Neural Networks

Artificial neural networks (ANN) mimic the human brain in a simulation tool that structures neural, just like the human brain. (Haykin,1994). Just like the human brain, which learns from experience, ANN learns by experiencing trends within the functionality of a system. Unlike traditional modelling methods, which use mathematical approaches to understand systems trends, ANN learns through an interactive process called training. Training, as suggested by the word, teaches ANN to learn specific relationships between the outputs and inputs of the system and understand how the system works.

Non-linear and linear transferred functions interconnect with a consistent number of artificial neurons; this allows ANN to be very capable of predicting behaviours of a system, particularly nonlinear behaviour. ANN has a multi-layered system called multi-layer feed-forward networking, and this networking characteristic is consistent with output and input layers and hidden layers within the functionality of a system (Cybenko,1989). Multiple hidden layers are not essential to occur within ANNs as one hidden layer of neurons is enough to allow ANN to approximate functions equally to a system with a sufficient number of neurons.

Network inputs will be presented and multiplied by adjustable weights, processed through the summed elements, and passed through a function of transfer which allows a product to be output. The input data will transfer through the network and, layer by layer, broken down to allow an obtained output. Outputs divide into two outcomes, desired output and actual outputs, the error within the data's output can be calculated by comparing both desired output and actual output. Calculations of the difference between each iteration of the term Epoch when using ANN allows the mean square error to calculate. If the mean squared error is deemed low, the training which allows ANN to learn and be relevant to system condition monitoring can be terminated due to the data being so low it would not be relevant when looking through the trend of the system. When the training has sufficient data and weights are deemed fixed within ANN, the ANN is ready to generalize outputs, which allows the network to perform as a condition monitoring method for the system. ANN can be seen in Figure 6 below, which shows low mean squared errors to be disregarded. However, using backpropagation ANN shown in Figure 7 can show weights to be adjusted.

Figure 6: ANN schematic (Agatonvic, 2000).

Mathematically error estimation by mean squared error can be defined as;

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{ii=1}^n (\hat{y}_{ii} - t_{ii})^2 \quad (1)$$

Y_i being the network output value n , total number respectively, t_i the target value. The smaller MSE value allows better ANN performance. (Agatonvic, 2000).

While ANN training occurs, any error within the network, returns through network to rectify the error and teach the network what is right from what is wrong within the system, this method is known as back propagation Artificial neural networks (BP-ANN) this can be shown schematically in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Back propagation process ANN (Li,2020).

3.5.2 Deep Transfer Learning

Showing the samples to be sectioned off and less confusing than a conventional method. Deep transferred learning aims to diagnose faults within a system by sharing fault knowledge from numerous turbines to determine a trend within the errors. This method is deemed difficult if looked at as a traditional data-driven method (Vapnik, 1999) due to turbines having different nominal parameters and fluctuating wildly on components characteristics and the size of the assembly. Figure 8 shows how transferred learning differs from conditional methods by comparing two gas turbines, A and B. Transferred learning allows the data distribution to map through solving the data. Thus, classified data is significantly reduced (Lu et al. 2015) for the system's performance they are showing.

Deep transfer learning allows sophisticated data to be memories without having to build a complicated system, this is done by numerous layers of data allowing fewer complex systems to learn and fault detect within the method. Deep transfer learning allows the use of 3 learning methods, reinforced, supervised, and unsupervised, with the computer obtaining data from previous experience of the trends of the system. This allows no formal requirement to input data required by the computer for tread monitoring. (Kim, 2022).

Figure 8: Deep transfer learning vs conventional learning (Kim, 2022).

3.5.3 Hybrid Methods

Hybrid methods of condition monitoring and fault diagnosis involve numerous methods combined to obtain the strongest means of finding faults by using two or more methods, this allows for the weakness of a certain method to be counterbalanced with the strengths of another method. A lot of hybrid methods are recommended in different combinations, this is dependent on the research and the outcome needed to be achieved (Kobayashi, Simon, 2005). Researchers. Singh and Sampath, implemented a method which involved integrating GA and ANN methods to diagnose fault within components of a Gas turbine and sensory failure. The results within this study demonstrated that both ANN and GA can work in combination to allow a 95% more accuracy for fault finding than if each method were to be utilized singular (Sampath, Singh, 2006).

Another example shown to utilize Hybrid methods can be Yulong Ying et al., where the combination of fuzzy-neural networks and neural-fuzzy systems were used, although these methods are not explained within this project, this combination can still be informative and highlight the many different methods conditioning monitoring can use. Yulong Ying et al. research and development of gas turbine diagnosis highlights when fault diagnosis reaches more than 95% fault within a single component, the embedded fault can be found within the design stage of a system (Ying et al. 2016).

3.6 Model-Driven Methods

3.6.1 Linear and nonlinear Kalman Filter (KF)

Gas turbine health monitoring and fault isolation first had Kalman filters introduced into the fault diagnoses in the late 1970s (Volponi et al. 2003). This simplistic method can be seen as the most common method when using data-driven monitoring methods estimating parameters of health within a gas turbine, this method can be seen below in figure 9, This method is used in numerous research where diagnosis of a system has obtained very good results when applied in a practical environment (Yang, et al. 2019), not only can this achieve accuracy when used in practical applications, but this method can also apply to theoretical properties and still obtain great accuracy with results (Togni et al. 2021).

Figure 9: Kalman filter (Ogaji, 2003).

Kalman filters require a long period of data from a system, measurements such as noise and other inaccuracies are known as unknown factors of estimate when dealing with Kalman filters (Dewallef et al. 2006). The introductory state along with noise is expected to be Gaussian when dealing with fundamental suspicions in linear data for Kalman filters. Data can eliminate issues by linearizing the current covariance and mean of the data by using extended Kalman filters or iterated Kalman filters. (Salilew et al. 2021).

3.6.2 Gas-Path Analysis

When Gas-path analysis is used linear, the method does not measure errors or relationships within the performance and engine monitoring of a gas turbine or jet engine. This method, invented by Urban (Urban, 1973), explores and monitors the relationship and performance of independent parameters through linear data, not accounting for the non-linearity of the data obtained. Research of current using gas path analysis is typically restricted to one discipline (Zhou et al. 2022), monitoring the performance degradation of the system by either thermodynamic or vibration faults within a gas turbine or jet engine. Although this method

has a strong background in monitoring and fault-finding mechanical and process defects, it has issues locating and isolating the point within the system due to its correlation to gas path fault diagnosis.

Gas path Analysis will assume that the faults within a system will degrade the components over time, from faults such as fouling and erosion, which will affect the output measurements of the gas turbine or jet engine. Therefore, the assembly of the components reviewed as a whole system, by gas path analysis treating the assembly as a system, the correlation between thermodynamic measurements and health parameters can be easily monitored. This system can monitor and detect faults using trend shifts. Trend shift is the most critical step within Gas path analysis, which Kobayashi, and Simon highlight in a study of engine health degradation (Kobayashi & Simon, 2007). Trend shift shows that if fault detection is not adaptive when monitoring a system, the diagnostic effectiveness of gas path analysis will become ineffective, and thus no data will be obtained to detect faults within a system.

3.6.3 Least Squares

Least squared methods Originally introduced by Karl Friedrich Gauss (Gauss 1809), the Least square method used for condition monitoring and fault finding within a gas turbine and jet engine estimates flow capacities and efficiency of the components within the system. The least squared methods can decrease uncertainties (Gao et al., 2021) when used as condition monitoring and fault-finding ways within gas turbines. When the least squared method and gas path examinations obtain data, the least squared method will heighten the exactness of the diagnostic. The measurement of problems within parameters, measured with the least squared calculation, can adjust additional parameters to induce solutions that become issue-free (Doel 2003).

3.7 Fault Detection

Fault finding within a Gas turbine and Jet engine system plays a vital role in minimising the operation and maintenance cost of the system due to high overhaul time intervals (Rasaenia,2013). It is helpful to run a system with the required measurement devices and instrumentation throughout the system, generating pre-alarms and detection techniques applicable to each Fault within the system.

Intelligent fault finding within a system can detect faults within a dynamic system by using numerous methods such as Transferred learning and neural networking, and these methods can learn the plant model from the input and output data or learn from real-time experiences programmed with the system. They can produce nonlinear functions (Sorsa, 1991) to construct the analytical model, but most importantly, they are used to perform fault detection within a system (Stengel, 1993).

The most important things to consider when fault detection of gas turbines and jet engines can be categorized into three topics.

1. Registered alarms are in such large amounts and status control of systems, analysing and predicting failure that can occur in the future are complicated.
2. Undesired changes in the efficiency and performance due to Fault within a system can affect the performance of numerous parts and locations within the system.
3. Performance reduction occurs due to time and aging efficiency within the turbines.

Fault identification can trigger the importance and extent of the Fault. Identification of a fault investigates the future life of the system or how critical the shutdown of the system is. The confidence in which shut down decisions are made depends on the condition monitoring method factored into the design (Vachtsevanos, 2006). Once the fault detection has happened within a system, fault identification (Bechini, 2010) is then forecasted by monitoring the behaviour of the Fault and the size/ magnitude of the problem within the system. Fault identification then leads to the final steps when condition monitoring, Fault is identified, allowing isolation of the system. Knowing the type of Fault and the components involved in the failure determines the importance of the operation and maintenance plan.

3.8 Sensor Faults

Faulty or unreliability within a system can result from sensor failure, the conditions of the turbine affected, which causes increased operation cost and a high impact on the system's downtime. Sensor faults typically happen due to harsh environments within which a turbine's service is. Sensor failure usually happens along with a degraded performance of the turbine. Thus, sensors fail simultaneously within a system (Ogaji et al. 2002).

Many gas turbines have integrated sensors for measuring data within the control system. This instrumentation measures the system's parameters depending on speed, pressure, power, and fuel flow rates. The number of sensors integrated into a system entirely depends on weight, installation cost, maintenance cost, and bulk within the system. (Fentaye et al., 2019) Due to the bulk of instrumentation within a system, the design stage of the turbine determines the critical areas which should be monitored, allowing several measurements to be made for diagnostic of the system (Jasmani, 2011).

3.9 Types of Faults

There are three main types of faults when dealing with a system incipient, intermittent, or abrupt fault (Isermann, 1997). Gas turbines tend to deal with incipient faults; these are faults that develop slowly over time and can be undetectable in the early stages of the fault. These faults can disguise themselves within a time-varying process (Ding, 2017). The faults within a gas turbine can then be subcategorised into sections of the operation, such as plant, actuator, or process faults (Gao et al. 2015), which can identify if the problems occur due to mechanical failure of an item within the turbine or the process operation causing the turbine to fail. This diagnosis can help select how maintenance should take place within the unit.

Abrupt faults in a system are inseparable when detecting and clearing the fault. When controlling the design stage of a gas turbine, these faults should be considered as they are

well-established problems within an assembly (Basseville, 1993). However, when dealing with incipient faults, a model monitoring system should be adopted to be an effective way of dealing with the fault, as, without a model of the system, data would be missing. The faults could not be detected until catastrophic failure occurred, which would cause the damage to be irreversible, which could cause severe effects depending on the location or if the turbine was industrial or aeronautical use which could be a crucial failure (Watanabe et al. 1989). Accipitral faults may not always exceed the threshold to be detectable within a system. However, if left untreated, depending on the location, size, or type of the error, this could cause significant degraded efficiency, which in turn causes economic losses to the system (Gautamet al. 2017).

Incipient fault amplitudes are small signals within a system that vary from 1% to 10% error and are regularly masked by variations of systems or disturbance of a different location. This can be a division when monitoring the system, which may be such a low magnitude that it is not recognizable when operational (Chen, 2018)

4.0 Failure mode and effective analysis FMEA background

FMEA within lean manufacturing is a tool to combat problems within a project. FMEA is used within conditioning monitoring as a technique of risk management that prevents failures within a system on certain levels by using remedial measurement (Kermanpur et al. 2008) methods to tackle each problem within a system. These measures can be used from the design stage through manufacturing until an operational system.

FMEA was first introduced into the aeronautical industry in the 1960s as a tool to control risk management during the design phase of a project. After other industries caught up with the system used within aeronautical industries, the automotive industry decided it would be good to adopt this system (Carter, 2005).

When introducing the FMEA process, the objective of this system is to distinguish which critical components are within the system and monitor the outputs to schedule predictive maintenance before catastrophic failure can occur. If this technique is implemented correctly and monitored, this can schedule plans for preventative maintenance.

In simple terms, the implementation of FMEA is as follows (Perkins, Bache 2005)

1. Recognizes failure modes that occur during the systems operations
2. Determine an explanation and reason as to why an error has occurred
3. Evaluate what effects the failures have on the system
4. Prioritize the importance of failure

The flow chart, Figure 10, shows the hierarchy of processes used within FMEA.

Figure 10: FMEA flow chart of hierarchic (Perkins, 2005).

FMEA is a tool for analyzing risks that have become a wise process to apply within many different engineering sectors. FMEA can include examining systems for failure modes within the performance of a system with defined characteristics, poor performance, or an undesired fault within a system that can affect people or the environment in which the system is located (Carlson,2014). Failure within the system with FMEA is identified within a scale monitoring the level of impact, multiple effects, top-level effects, and minor effects. Multiple faults in the system can coincide; however, due to the structure designed with the FMEA approach, the structure concentrates on the effect of the problems and inflicts the most critical damage to the system if left unnoticed. If the system components are considered along with the effect of the failure, this can then be seen as failure mode effects and criticality Analysis (FMECA).

The approached FMEA structure, as shown in figure 6, generalizes the approach of FMEA. Figure 11 is a bottom-up approach to analyzing hazards, which is a powerful tool for risk analysis of a model. (Singh,2014).

Figure 11: FMEA bottom-up approach (Hassan et al. 2022).

Gas turbine examples of failures can include compressor contamination, thermocouple sensor faults, HP turbine seal damage, and Fuel actuator friction wear, all replicated within the simulation used in section 4.0 of this report. The severity of each fault could be catastrophic, critical, or marginal. Using FMEA is linked to the effects number assigned to the problem occurring. Effects numbers in whichever stage of a project's life, including decommissioning, operations, installation, and design, FMEA in the design stage is deemed the most critical as if a design has errors, this can affect the processes after that.

FMEA, when used within different stages of a project, can change the risk factors within the system, as when used during the design stage, effects on the system can be highlighted, which could cause a costly re-design stage when a failure occurs. FMEA used within the testing stage

can be used to identify weaknesses within a system and rectified using risk priority. Risk priority assessments calculated the quality risk prioritization number (RPN), deriving a product from three ratings of likelihood, the severity, and the detectability of a failure within the systems operations (Hassan et al. 2022). RPN allows a hierarchy of importance to how critical a failure is within the system by allocating a qualitative number to the problem which can occur. FMEA is often based on the expertise of the assembly team of the system. Each parameter can agree within the design and installation of the team when FMEA is running for fault finding within a gas turbine.

Examples of ranking criteria are as shown below in Tables 2, 3, and 4 (Norske & Veritas, 2010)

Table 2: Failure detectability ranking.

Detection Level	Description	Ranking
Highly Likely	Controls will almost certainly detect failure.	1
Likely	High chance for the design controls to detect failure.	2
Reasonably Likely	Reasonably likely chance for the design controls to detect failure.	3
Unlikely	Remote chance for the design controls to detect failure.	4
Highly Unlikely	Very remote chance for the design controls to detect failure.	5

Table 3: Failure Severity Ranking.

Severity Level	Description	Ranking
Negligible	A failure mode could potentially degrade the system's functions but will cause no damage to the system and does not constitute a threat to life or injury.	1
Marginal	System operational with minor performance degradation.	2
Moderate	A failure mode, which could potentially degrade system performance function(s) without damage to the system or threat to life or injury.	3
Critical	A failure mode could potentially result in the failure of the system's primary functions and therefore cause considerable damage to the system and its environment, but which does not constitute a serious threat to life or injury.	4
Catastrophic	A failure mode could potentially result in the failure of the system's primary functions and therefore cause serious damage to the system and its environment and/or personal injury.	5

Table 4: Failure likelihood ranking.

Likelihood Level	Description	Probability	Ranking
Very Low	Failure unlikely	$\leq 1 \times 10^{-5}$	1
Low	Relatively few failures	1×10^{-4}	2
Average	Occasional failures	1×10^{-3}	3
High	Repeated failures	1×10^{-2}	4
Very High	Failure is almost inevitable	$\geq 1 \times 10^{-1}$	5

5.0 Gas Turbine Model Simulation

The model used within this project involves having three initial conditions with initial condition 1, allowing speeded-up parameters to investigate dynamic performance within the system, initial conditions 2 and 3 providing validation against steady-state conditions from two engines being case 1 and case 2, all with steady-state values (Simani & Patton 2008). The four common faults are used within the system.

1. Compressor contamination
2. Thermocouple sensor fault
3. HP turbine seal damage
4. Fuel actuator friction wear

The simple structure of the model and speeded-up parameters make the model structure suitable to perform remotely and online (Bettocchi, Spina, & Fabbri, 1996).

To understand the data produced, it is essential to familiarize the variables of the system. These are shown in Table 5. For the units of variables, Appendix A can be cross-referenced for the relative information

Table 5 function of variants and abbreviations within the data

FUNCTION	ABBREVIATIONS
AMBIENT AIR TEMP	t1
AMBIENT PRESSURE	p1
FUEL FLOW	ff
TURBINE BACK PRESSURE	p7
TURBINE COOLING AIR FLOW (OUTPUT)	m10
TURBINE COOLING TEMP (OUTPUT)	t4
TURBINE OUTLET MASS FLOW	m8
TURBINE OUTLET MASS TEMP	t7n
TURBINE SPEED	Wt
PRESSURISING VALVE MASS FLOW	m9
VALVE UP STREAM PRESSURE	p7
VALVE UP STREAM TEMP	t7

VALVE ANGLE	av
VALVE DOWNSTREAM PRESSURE	p8
COMBUSTION OUTPUT TEMPERATURE	t5c
COMBUSTION INLET TEMPERATURE	t5

The model simulation which has been used, can be shown below which each condition and fault can be introduced by a simple double click on the box wishing to obtain conditions from, if a fault is to be added then once initial condition has been selected, then double clicking the fault to be simulated shall be introduced into the system, Appendix A can show the operations manual for the simulation.

Figure 12: Simulink Model layout of gas turbine.

5.1 Initial Condition Comparison

Initial conditions 1,2 & 3 all have different pressure outputs from the compressor before the pressure output reaches the turbine, all three of these initial conditions have different values due to variable differences within the system which allows 3 different turbines to be replicated in this study. In Figure 13, an example of each initial condition with pressure vs time within the compressor is shown, this is to replicate that all three initial conditions run differently.

Figure 13: compressor pressure vs time for 3 initial conditions.

Due to the control loop within the simulation when faults are introduced to the system, this replicates incipient faults thus not allowing a noticeable change to show for a comparison of what effect the fault has within the system.

The model schematic which was used within a project can be seen with PID control, a compressor map and a turbine map which are the control feedback causing the systems faults to be corrected this is replicated schematically in Figure 14. The nomenclature table for this diagram can be obtained within Appendix B which will show the abbreviation of the diagram for better understanding.

Figure 14: Schematic of turbine simulation (Simani & Patton 2008).

5.2 Fault Case 1

Fault one, when plotted with mass flow m_3 vs time, can be shown that the fault and initial condition two have the same data due to the control system this can be shown in Figure 15, when fault 1 represents fouling on the compressor blade which in a gas turbine system reduces airflow, thus changing the blades aerodynamics, as the roughness of the blade due to contamination causes friction which affects airflow.

Figure 15: Mass flow m3 fault vs initial condition 2.

5.3 Fault Case 2

Fault 2 is a malfunction of the thermocouple, which is a common problem within gas turbines, which occurs with high maintenance. It can be seen that variable t3n which is indicated in the HTDU turbine block as fail 2 within the simulation, this fault decreases or increases over time through the leading gas path, however in this simulation due to the error being so small it can be shown graphically as the same magnitude as initial condition when comparing the data shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: T3n initial condition 1 and fault 2 vs time.

5.4 Fault Case 3

Fault case 3 represents a Failure of the HP turbine seal, which affects the efficiency of the turbine, the model can be shown to affect the efficiency over time, however when fault condition and initial condition are compared within the turbine the control system of the turbine causes a steady state comparison, causing the results to carry the same path, therefore the comparison of the data is unachievable for this fault. This can be shown in Figure 17

Figure 17: Fault case 3 and initial condition 1 efficiency vs time.

5.5 Fault Case 4

Within fault case 4 variable fuel flow (FF) has been compared to initial condition 1, the difference is very hard to detect due to the governor compensating the effect of the fault within the simulation, fault 4 simulates loss of performance due to actuator wear within the valves actuator, due to the simulation having no actuator dynamic factored into the design, the effects of the actuator wear cause slower response on the modelled flow rates, again with fault 4 when graphically shown the control within the system makes the faults impossible to compare. This can be shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Fault 4 and initial condition fuel flow vs time.

Simulation of a gas turbine is a great tool in modelling faults and conditions in different timescales, to allow speed of analysis of the data obtained, as the following fault conditions in real industrial application can develop slowly over periods of months, to avoid excessively long simulation timescales, the faults rate of development will be increased that the effects will be visible within an hour of the simulation period.

6.0 Discussion of Gas Turbine Achievements

Creating and developing the correct methods of conditioning monitoring and fault diagnosis within gas turbine and jet engine systems can be deemed a particularly complex task with many methods to consider when choosing the right style for the subject monitoring. With performance-based methods saving time within maintenance and operations schedules, thus reducing cost, these methods combined with FMEA can allow the downtime of a system to stay minimal and the safety of a system due to the task planned through the urgency of the fault within the gas turbine. FMEA can be used not only within condition monitoring of gas turbines and jet engines but can also play a role within a lean management system, helping to produce a forward plan from design through to decommissioning, saving cost and time where relevant through the life cycle of a gas turbine.

Although industrial turbines and jet engines have similar properties, preventative maintenance is paramount when dealing with jet engines. Jet engines cannot allow for catastrophic failure due to the consequence of a system failure which could cause severe injury and even death to people relying on the soundness of the system; therefore, when dealing with jet engines, preventative maintenance should be a priority. FMEA severity ranking is considered when planning of the servicing of gas turbines and jet engines. When dealing with jet engines, sensors should be changed when in service for a short time, as a faulty sensor can cause a system to fail catastrophically when not monitoring a system correctly.

If an industrial turbine were to fail, this could cause complications and costly downtime due to the complexity of a system; however, if catastrophic failure were to occur within a system, the system would typically change over to the reserve turbine, although this would be an expensive failure, the effect of failure in industrial turbines affects components and turbines output, unlike jet engines which could cause a high severity within the system. Located on the same site the reserved turbine can run correctly while the failed turbine is deemed 'offline' while the diagnostic and servicing takes place. However, this is not standard practice within the industry but will reduce the loss of earnings for the site the turbine is located within. Like jet engines, industrial systems have a preventative maintenance plan to lower costs and can allow planned maintenance when the turbine does not need to produce an output.

The two main objectives for trend monitoring are to save costs for the maintenance of a system and to increase the reliability of data from the accuracy and diagnostics of faults. The planned maintenance for industrial turbines and jet engines through monitoring trends within the systems operations. The faults studied within this project are incipient, as the margin of error is so tiny these faults running within the system may cause further complications due to the modelling method used. Therefore, if fault monitoring using a hybrid data-driven method, numerous combined methods have a very high diagnosis when condition monitoring a system and fault diagnosis, the data obtained would be very useful when understanding why the fault has occurred and the location of the fault, thus allowing a cost-effective maintenance plan.

7.0 Conclusion of the Gas Turbine Case Study

Gas turbines are very complex systems that, if faults are left undetected/ untreated, can become a very severe and costly problem for both industrial and jet engines. This project has shown that different methods of condition monitoring can allow faults to be found and treated accordingly through FMEA, FMEA, and condition monitoring can save time, cost, and catastrophe within the workings of a gas turbine and jet engine. Incipient faults can hide within a system's trend due to the marginal error the fault produces, which in time can cause failure to the components of the system not only within the area of the fault but also throughout the gas turbine, thus causing costly damage to the system. Therefore, susceptible condition monitoring methods such as combined hybrid should be applied within a system to ensure all faults become detected at the earliest possible time. Along with using a condition monitoring method that detects a fault with compassionate data application, gas turbines and jet engines should also have planned maintenance, using FMEA to ensure that all critical sensors and components are in complete working order. Throughout the life cycle, catastrophic failure can cause significant problems to a system and the people reliant on the jet engine's performance, such as pilots or passengers on an aircraft.

8.0 Application to Wind Turbine Fleets

8.1 Summary of Wind Turbine Fleets

The installed wind power capacity is growing in many countries. Remote condition monitoring of wind turbines is employed to achieve high uptimes and low maintenance costs. Data-driven machine learning models are in use in monitoring centers to detect developing damages in wind turbines. Training these fault detection models requires large amounts of past and present operation data. However, the required data are often lacking or not representative. Wind farms at the beginning of their operation life lack data from past operations. Older turbines may also lack enough representative training data as a result of control software updates and hardware replacements. Following such events, a turbine's operation behavior can change significantly so the operation data from the turbine's past operation may no longer be representative of its current operation behavior. To overcome this lack of data for training fault detection models, we propose to re-use and transfer knowledge about the normal operation behaviour of a turbine with sufficient training data to turbines with insufficient training data. We demonstrate that cross-turbine transfer learning can drastically improve the accuracy of fault detection models in turbines with scarce operation data. Using the combined operation knowledge from turbines with scarce and with sufficient operation data enables an earlier data-driven detection of faults than the prior art methods.

8.2 Introduction to Wind Turbines

The globally installed wind power capacity is growing steadily, in line with efforts to increase the share of renewable energy production around the world (IEA, 2021a,b). The operation and maintenance costs of wind farms make up about one-third of the electricity production costs over the lifetime of a wind farm (Karyotakis, 2011). Condition monitoring and intelligent fault detection approaches can enable a transition towards condition-based maintenance of wind turbines, thereby increasing the uptime of the monitored turbines and reducing their maintenance costs. Fault detection algorithms that rely on machine learning are designed to trigger a notification to the operator when unusual operation behaviour is observed. This requires models of the turbine's normal operation behavior which can be trained on condition data from healthy wind turbines. The use of condition data from the supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) system was successfully demonstrated to train such normal behaviour models for fault detection tasks (e.g., Zaher et al., 2009; Schlechtingen et al., 2013; Stetco et al., 2019; Tautz-Weinert et al., 2018; Meyer, 2021a,b).

However, this approach requires condition monitoring data to be available over a sufficiently long operation period and cover a representative range of operating conditions. Indeed, when condition monitoring data are scarce or when they are no longer representative of the turbine's current behaviour, then fault detection based on normal behaviour models (NBM) is usually not an option because NBM cannot be trained then. This is the case for newly commissioned turbines and in the initial stage of the turbine operation life.

Moreover, major changes in the operating conditions can result in a lack of SCADA data representative of the past operation, at any turbine age. This scenario can arise after control software updates or hardware retrofits, for example.

This report demonstrates the potential of transfer learning which enables SCADA-based fault detection with normal behavior models even when condition data are scarce.

We investigate how Normal Behaviour Models (NBM)s can be transferred from a turbine with extensive training data (source WT) to a turbine with scarce operation data (target WT) to accomplish accurate NBM and, thus, reduce fault detection delays. We propose and investigate multiple transfer strategies and study how they affect NBM accuracy. We also investigate how the most preferable transfer strategy depends on the scarcity of the training data. Our proposed approach drastically reduces the amount of condition data required to train an NBM for fault detection tasks. We demonstrate that transfer learning results in a higher NBM accuracy and, thus, earlier fault detection when less than a year of training data is available.

This report is organized as follows. Section 8.3 reviews transfer learning approaches and why they are beneficial in wind power applications. We also review recently proposed first applications of transfer learning to condition monitoring tasks in wind power plants. SCADA-based modelling of the normal operation behaviour and detection of deviations from that behaviour is one of the most relevant fault detection approaches in WTs in practice (Tautz-Weinert et al., 2017). Despite its relevance, the potential of transfer learning for this fault detection task has not been investigated so far. This report demonstrates how transfer learning can be beneficial for extracting operation knowledge from turbines with sufficient training data and for re-using this knowledge to improve the fault detection accuracy in turbines with scarce training data. Thus, Section 8.4 introduces new transfer-based fault detection strategies for turbines with scarce training data. We present a case study that compares the strategies and discuss the result. Finally, Section 8.5 presents our conclusions and directions for future research on the application of wind turbines.

8.3 Problem Formulation for Wind Turbine Fleets

Fault detection methods for wind turbines (WT) usually assume that the training and the test data originate from the same multivariate distribution in the same feature space. For instance, it is often assumed that a model of the WT's normal operation behaviour, once trained on past operation data, will continue to perform well when applied to data from the future operation of the turbine. However, this assumption is often not correct in practice as the distribution of the operation data can evolve. This can be reflected in distribution shifts, such as shifts in the power curve or in other correlated SCADA variables. Various processes can cause these distribution changes, including control software updates, part replacements, and degradation processes that affect the turbine's normal operation behaviour. In such situations, SCADA data that are representative of the current normal operation of the WT is scarce. Representative SCADA data is also scarce after the WT commissioning and at the beginning of its operation life. Likewise, representative condition data is often scarce after major repairs, after control software updates, and after changes in the WT ownership and data loss events.

Changes in the environmental conditions may also result in a scarcity of representative WT condition data. Environmental conditions may change, for example, following an extension of the wind farm.

If condition data is barely available, the feature space will be populated only scarcely, so a probability density distribution that is representative of the WT's normal operation behaviour cannot be estimated reliably. For instance, we might not have enough SCADA data taken at high wind speeds, so we cannot accurately estimate a power curve. On the other hand, after software and hardware updates, condition data from past operations are often plentifully available but no longer representative of the current operation behaviour.

In this case, the feature space is comprehensively populated, but the distribution of the data does not fully reflect the WT's current normal operation behavior. If we nevertheless train an NBM on the past operation data, it will be less capable of detecting anomalous operation behaviour and, thus, cause delays in the detection of incipient faults (Meyer, 2021b).

More formally, transfer learning relies on the mathematical concepts of domain and task. A domain $D = \{X, P(X)\}$ consists of a feature space X and a marginal probability distribution $P(X)$. A task T is defined by a label set Y and a conditional probability distribution $P(Y|X)$ which can be estimated from a training set $\{(x_i, y_i) \mid x_i \in X, y_i \in Y\}$. Transfer learning considers a source domain D_s , a target domain D_t , source task T_s and a target task T_t , and aspires to estimate the conditional probability distribution in the target domain, $P(Y_t|X_t)$ from information extracted from the source domain $D_s = \{X_s, P(X_s)\}$ and tasks T_s, T_t (Dai et al., 2007; Pan et al., 2010). Thus, it enables the transfer of information learnt on a source feature space and task to a different but related target feature space and task. In this way, it can help to address mismatches in the training and the test data.

9.0 Automatic Control Applications to Offshore Floating Wind Turbine Fleets

9.1 Summary

Floating Offshore Wind Turbines (FOWTs) have developed rapidly because they are suitable for deep sea and have high power generation efficiency. However, the control of FOWTs is also very tricky. The main challenges include the difficulty of accurate modelling of FOWTs and the higher failure rate of components. Therefore, this project proposes a model-free adaptive fault-tolerant control scheme for blade root moment sensor faults. Through a model-free adaptive control strategy, an individual pitch controller and a fault compensator are designed to avoid the mathematical modelling of FOWT. The proposed fault-tolerant control scheme does not need any fault diagnosis and isolation and transforms the fault dynamic compensation process into a real-time control problem for nonlinear systems. The proposed control strategy is simulated and tested by FAST, and the results show that the proposed strategy can not only keep the bearing load of the wheel balanced but also reduce the movement of the floating platform and significantly reduce the bearing load of the FOWT. In addition, the output power is closer to the rated power, which verifies the excellent fault tolerance capability of the strategy under multiple blade root moment sensor failures. Therefore, this report will investigate the development of a model-free adaptive fault-tolerant control for the FOWT considered here with multiple blade root moment sensor faults.

9.2 Introduction to Offshore Floating Wind Turbines

Wind energy has gradually become the mainstream energy production form to meet future social needs (Pöschke et al., 2022). Compared with onshore wind power generation, offshore wind power generation can obtain more abundant wind energy resources and higher power conversion efficiency and has the advantages of green environmental protection. Therefore, the technology of offshore wind power generation has entered a rapid development stage (He et al., 2020). Compared with offshore fixed pile wind turbines, the advantages of floating offshore wind turbines (FOWTs) are obvious in terms of economy, ease of installation and large capacity, especially in deep water (Campanile et al., 2018). However, FOWT is subject to higher structural and fatigue loads due to the greater compliance of large structures and highly asymmetric wind loads. This increased load can lead to rapid wear or damage of structural components, reduced service life, and increased maintenance costs (Qiao et al., 2015).

The traditional variable speed rotor and collective pitch control (CPC) technology have limited control over the fatigue load of wind turbines due to rotor yaw error, shaft tilt, wind shear and turbulence (Badihi et al., 2021). Therefore, individual pitch control (IPC) technology is used to cope with highly complex operational loads in FOWTs without affecting power generation (Zhang et al., 2021). Namik et al. (2008) used the IPC strategy to design a state feedback controller (SFC) by formulating the dynamics of barge-type FOWT in the form of state space, to explore the feasibility of applying IPC-based SFC to optimize system operation.

Chaaban et al. (2013, 2014) used the model predictive control (MPC) method to design an individual pitch controller to solve the problem of equivalent fatigue load of blades and platform behaviour when manipulating rotor speed. Yang et al. (2014) proposed a new IPC method, which combines wind suppression disturbance regulation controller (DAC) and MPC to predict and compensate for the impact of wind wave disturbance.

Sarkar et al. (2020) adopted a new IPC technology based on wavelet LQR (W-LQR) to solve the conflict between speed and torque control requirements of spar-type FOWT for the first time. Gutierrez et al. (2022) proposed an adaptive second-order sliding mode control algorithm based on the super-torsion control law, which has a very small number of adjustment parameters and low computational requirements.

The IPC methods reported in the above studies assume that all components are in satisfactory operating conditions and that all states are measurable. However, the harsh offshore meteorological conditions and the design of the floating structure make the sensors and actuators in FOWT operation susceptible to failures (Li et al., 2022). To allow FOWTs to maintain system performance in case of failure, fault-tolerant control techniques (Kamarzarrin et al., 2022; Jain et al., 2020) are applied to individual pitch control, which is called fault-tolerant individual pitch control (FTIPC), and only a few studies have been published. Bachinski et al. (2013) first applied FTC to spar-type FOWT with the pitch actuator failed. Cho et al. (2018) proposed an FTIPC method based on Kalman filter and threshold H_2/H_∞ technology to deal with the fault of the pitch angle sensor and actuator of spar-type FOWT. Liu et al. (2020) combined a model-based fault diagnosis method with subspace predictive repetitive control and proposed a new fast adaptive FTIPC method to solve the stuck fault of the pitch actuator. Whether for pitch angle sensor failure or pitch actuator failure, the above studies rely on the model information of the controlled system and require fault diagnosis, fault isolation, or parameter estimation to construct fault-tolerant control strategies.

For the FOWT with the full coupling of aero-hydro-servo-elastic dynamics under the combined action of wind, wave and current, modelling/estimation errors or unmodeled dynamics are inevitable, so there are still deficiencies in the application of the above fault-tolerant schemes to FOWTs. In addition, although the pitch sensors and actuators considered in the above studies are critical to the realization of the IPC scheme, the failures of blade root moment sensors may be ignored. The performance improvement of the blade root moment sensor is a challenge in the IPC system, which plays a key role in reducing the uneven blade load of large wind turbines, especially for offshore wind turbines (OWTs) operating in harsh environments such as lightning, salt spray, humidity and corrosion. OWT has a higher failure rate of blade load sensors with an average of one failure per year. For OWTs with three blades, the failure rate is approximately three failures per year (Wei et al., 2008). Stotsky et al. (2014) proposed a blade root moment sensor fault detection method that relies on the blade load model and light detection and ranging (LIDAR). Wei et al. (2008) investigated the problem of blade root moment sensor fault detection based on the Kalman filter. However, the design of fault-tolerant control methods is not included in any of the above studies.

Motivated by the above problems, this project proposes a model-free adaptive fault-tolerant IPC scheme for blade root moment sensor faults without any prior modelling of FOWTs. As an adaptive fault-tolerant control strategy, the proposed scheme is different from the traditional passive fault-tolerant control that only aims at specific types of faults and the active fault-tolerant control strategy relies on fault diagnosis and isolation, does not need any fault detection and diagnosis, and dynamically recovers multiple blade root moment sensor faults through the adaptive compensator. Specifically, the contributions of this project are as follows.

1. An individual pitch controller is designed based on a model-free adaptive control method, which does not rely on the model information of FOWTs and effectively avoids the adverse effects caused by modelling errors and unmodeled dynamics.
2. A blade root moment sensor fault compensator is developed, which does not need any fault diagnosis and isolation. The dynamic fault compensation process is transformed into a nonlinear system real-time control problem.
3. The model-free adaptive fault-tolerant individual pitch control scheme consisting of the above controller and fault compensator is extensively tested in FAST, which verified its effectiveness and robustness under the fixed deviation fault, drift deviation fault, complete failure and coexistence of multiple faults of blade root moment sensor.

The rest of this report is organized as follows. Section 9.3 reviews the FOWT benchmark and the types of blade root moment sensor failure. In Section 9.4, a model-free adaptive fault-tolerant individual pitch control scheme for FOWT is proposed. The simulation results are presented and discussed in Section 9.5. Section 9.6 concludes the report.

9.3 Benchmark model of the FOWT and Blade Root Moment Sensor Failures

9.3.1 The benchmark model of FOWT

The numerical model adopted in this report is the OC4-Deepcwind semi-submersible floating wind turbine developed by the University of Maine (Coulling et al., 2013), as shown in Figure 1. The wind turbine model is the famous NREL 5 MW wind turbine. The parameters of the wind turbine and the semi-submersible floating platform are shown in Table 1 and Table 2. The nonlinear model of the FOWT with all the above parts combined has 22 degrees of freedom (DOF). The details of the dynamic modelling of the 22-DOF system are not shown in this report, and the detailed modelling details can be found in Jonkman (2007).

Figure 1: The structure of OC4-DeepCwind semi-submersible floating wind turbine.

Table 1 Parameters of 5MW offshore floating wind turbine of NREL.

Attribute	Value
Cut-in Speed $/(m \cdot s^{-1})$	3
Rated Speed $/(m \cdot s^{-1})$	11.4
Cut-out Speed $/(m \cdot s^{-1})$	25
Rotor Diameter/m	63
Rated Power/MW	5
Rated Rotor Speed $/(r \cdot min^{-1})$	12.1
Rated generator Speed $/(r \cdot min^{-1})$	1.1737×10^3
Transmission Ratio	97:1

Table 2 Parameters of the semi-submersible floating platform.

Attribute	Value
Draft/m	20
Elevation of platform top above SWL/m	10
Depth to top of base columns below SWL/m	14
Platform mass/kg	13444000
Displacement $/m^3$	13986
Center of mass below SWL/m	14.4
Platform roll inertia $/(kg \cdot m^2)$	8.011×10^9
Platform pitch inertia $/(kg \cdot m^2)$	8.011×10^9
Platform yaw inertia $/(kg \cdot m^2)$	1.391×10^9

9.3.2 Blade root moment sensor failures

For FOWTs with individual pitch control systems, the failure of the blade root moment sensor can lead to unreasonable blade pitch angles, unbalancing the wheel rotation and potentially resulting in poor performance or damage to the wind turbine, so proper functioning of the blade root moment sensor is critical for successful individual pitch control applications. As shown in Figure 2, blade root moment sensor failures include four categories: decreased accuracy, fixed bias, drift bias, and complete failure (Yang et al., 2022). Among them, fixed bias and drift bias failures are not easy to detect and can cause a series of unpredictable problems, making the system not work properly for a long time. Therefore, in this project, we mainly consider fixed bias, drift bias faults and complete failure, and all three types of faults can be equated to the following functions when taking $a_c(k)$ a suitable dynamic value.

$$M_m(k) = a_c(k) \cdot M_a(k) \quad (9.1)$$

where $M_m(k)$ is the measured blade root moment, $M_a(k)$ is the true blade root moment and $a_c(k)$ is the dynamic equivalent fault factor, and the sensor is fault-free when $a_c(k)=1$.

Figure 2: The types of blade root moment sensor failure

9.4 Model-free adaptive fault-tolerant control for the floating offshore wind turbine

As described in Section 9.3, although the mathematical model of the FOWT can be obtained by using the dynamics theory, the model verification is challenging. In addition, obtaining a control model to represent the operating state of the FOWT under random meteorological conditions is rather difficult. Thus, the individual pitch controller (IPC) and fault adaptive compensator are designed using MFAC without any modelling of the FOWT in this section, to achieve adaptive fault-tolerant pitch control of FOWTs under the blade root moment sensor faults described in Section 9.3.

9.4.1 Individual pitch control

IPC is usually realized by feedback of blade root bending moment. Specifically, the blade root bending moment in the rotating coordinate system is converted into the tilt and yaw components in the fixed coordinate system by Coleman transformation, as shown in (9.2). The tilt and yaw control quantities are obtained by designing a reasonable controller.

After the Coleman transform, the pitch system can be represented as a discrete system as follows (9.3):

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_{\text{tilt}} \\ M_{\text{yaw}} \end{bmatrix} \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \cos(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \cos(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \\ \sin(\theta) & \sin(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \sin(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} M_{m,1} \\ M_{m,2} \\ M_{m,3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9.2)$$

$$M_{t\&y}(k+1) = f(M_{t\&y}(k), \dots, M_{t\&y}(k-n_{p1}), u_{t\&y}(k), \dots, u_{t\&y}(k-n_{q1})) \quad (9.3)$$

where $f(\cdot)$ is the unknown nonlinear function, n_{p1} and n_{q1} are the coefficients.

According to the MFAC (Wang et al., 2020; Li et al., 2021), the system (9.3) can be expressed as (4). Under the conditions that the system is controllable and observable, the partial derivative of the control input signal exists, and the system is continuous and satisfies the generalized Lipschitz assumption, considering the control input criterion function expressed in (9.6) and the estimation criterion function of the pseudo derivative expressed in (9.7), the IPC based on the compact format linearization method expressed in (9.8)-(9.10) can be given:

$$\Delta M_{t\&y}(k+1) = \Phi_1(k) \cdot \Delta u_{t\&y}(k) \quad (9.4)$$

$$\Phi_1(k) = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{11}(k) & \phi_{12}(k) \\ \phi_{21}(k) & \phi_{22}(k) \end{bmatrix} \quad (9.5)$$

$$J(u_{t\&y}(k)) = \|M_{t\&y}^*(k+1) - M_{t\&y}(k+1)\|^2 + \lambda_1 \|u_{t\&y}(k) - u_{t\&y}(k-1)\|^2 \quad (9.6)$$

$$J(\Phi_1(k)) = \|M_{t\&y}(k) - M_{t\&y}(k-1) - \Phi_1(k) \cdot \Delta u_{t\&y}(k-1)\|^2 + \mu_1 \|\Phi_1(k) - \hat{\Phi}_1(k-1)\|^2 \quad (9.7)$$

$$\hat{\Phi}_1(k) = \hat{\Phi}_1(k-1) + \frac{\eta_1 \Delta u_{t\&y}(k-1)}{\mu_1 + \|\Delta u_{t\&y}(k-1)\|^2} \cdot (\Delta M_{t\&y}(k) - \hat{\Phi}_1(k-1) \Delta u_{t\&y}(k-1)) \quad (9.8)$$

$$\hat{\Phi}_1(k) = \hat{\Phi}_1(1), \text{ if } |\hat{\Phi}_1(k)| < \varepsilon, \text{ or } |\Delta u_{t\&y}(k-1)| < \varepsilon \quad (9.9)$$

$$u_{t\&y}(k) = u_{t\&y}(k-1) + \frac{\rho_1 \hat{\Phi}_1(k)}{\lambda_1 + \|\hat{\Phi}_1(k)\|^2} (M_{t\&y}^*(k+1) - M_{t\&y}(k)) \quad (9.10)$$

where λ_1 is a positive weighting factor, $M^*(k+1)$ is the reference output at $k+1$, μ_1 is a positive weighting factor, and $\Phi_1(k-1)$ is an estimate of the pseudo derivative at $k-1$; η_1 and ρ_1 denote the sequence of steps, respectively, and ε is a sufficiently small positive number.

The IPC components $\Delta\beta = [\Delta\beta_1 \ \Delta\beta_2 \ \Delta\beta_3]^T$ of the three blades obtained through inverse Coleman transformation from $u_{t\&y}(k)$ obtained from the above IPC:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta\beta_1 \\ \Delta\beta_2 \\ \Delta\beta_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \sin(\theta) \\ \cos(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \sin(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) \\ \cos(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) & \sin(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} u_{\text{tilt}}(k) \\ u_{\text{yaw}}(k) \end{bmatrix} \quad (9.11)$$

9.5 Blade root moment fault adaptive compensator

From (9.1), it can be seen that all types of sensor faults can be described by the equivalent fault factor a_c . Similarly, all sensor faults can be offset by the equivalent compensation factor r_{ac} to the effect of the equivalent fault factor a_c . Theoretically, r_{ac} and a_c should be reciprocal, so the focus of this section is to design an adaptive compensator to solve for the equivalent compensation factor r_{ac} to compensate for the blade root moment sensors dynamically in real-time.

As shown in Figure 3(a), when there is no fault in the blade root moment sensor, the three-blade root moment varies periodically, they are the same except for the phase difference of $2\pi/3$. When the blade root moment sensor failure occurs, the inaccurate moment value is fed back to the individual pitch controller to derive an unreasonable pitch angle command, resulting in an imbalance of the load on the three blades, and this imbalance of the root waving load in the rotating coordinate system can be intuitively obtained by the Coleman transformation and its inverse conversion as expressed in (9.12).

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta M_{m,1} \\ \Delta M_{m,2} \\ \Delta M_{m,3} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \sin(\theta) \\ \cos(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \sin(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) \\ \cos(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) & \sin(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \cos(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \cos(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \\ \sin(\theta) & \sin(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \sin(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} M_{m,1} \\ M_{m,2} \\ M_{m,3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9.12)$$

Figure 3: Blade root moment M_m and transformed moment ΔM_m under fault-free and fault scenarios

Figure 3 (b) shows the balanced performance of ΔM_m under the condition of fault-free. When sensor 1 has a slight fault of $a_{c,1}=0.8$, as shown in Figure 3 (c) and 3 (d), the output value of blade 1 root flapping moment in Figure 3 (c) is smaller than that of blades 2 and 3, and the three blades' flapping moment M_m is slightly unbalanced. From Figure 3 (d), it can be seen that $\Delta M_{m,1}$ is obviously smaller than the other two, and the sensor 1 fault will also affect the blade root load of blades 2 and 3, and ΔM_m has an obvious imbalance. The degree of this imbalance can be quantified by the mean value of ΔM_m . Taking the 18m/s average turbulent wind as an example, the mean value of ΔM_m under different faults of sensor 1 is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: The mean value of ΔM_m under different fault scenarios of sensor 1

Fault scenario	Equivalent fault factor	Ideal equivalent compensation factor	$\Delta M_{m,1}$	$\Delta M_{m,2}$	$\Delta M_{m,3}$
$a_{c,1} < 0$	$a_{c,1}=0.50$	$r_{a_{c,1}}=2.00$	-1518.43	635.60	882.83
	$a_{c,1}=0.70$	$r_{a_{c,1}}=1.43$	-843.43	346.54	496.89
	$a_{c,1}=0.90$	$r_{a_{c,1}}=1.11$	-268.21	109.87	158.34
fault-free	$a_{c,1}=1.00$	$r_{a_{c,1}}=1.00$	28.50	-13.55	-14.95
$a_{c,1} > 0$	$a_{c,1}=1.10$	$r_{a_{c,1}}=0.90$	228.91	-93.00	-135.91
	$a_{c,1}=1.30$	$r_{a_{c,1}}=0.77$	662.71	-262.75	-399.96
	$a_{c,1}=1.50$	$r_{a_{c,1}}=0.67$	1044.41	-443.53	-600.88

From Table 3 it can be concluded that, whether it is $a_{c,1} < 0$ faults or $a_{c,1} > 0$ faults, with the serious increase of faults, the deviation between the average value of ΔM_m increases, which corresponds to the equivalent fault factor $a_{c,1}$ in a nonlinear manner. Similarly, it also has a nonlinear relationship with the equivalent compensation factor $r_{ac,1}$. The nonlinear relationship of ΔM_m and $r_{ac,1}$ can be described as the nonlinear discrete system described in (9.13).

$$\Delta M_m(k+1) = f(\Delta M_m(k), \dots, \Delta M_m(k-n_{p2}), r_{ac}(k), \dots, r_{ac}(k-n_{q2})) \quad (9.13)$$

where n_{p2} and n_{q2} coefficients. $\Delta M_m(k) = [\Delta M_{m,1}(k), \Delta M_{m,2}(k), \Delta M_{m,3}(k)]^T$ is the output data at time k , and $r_{ac}(k) = [r_{ac1}(k) \ r_{ac2}(k) \ r_{ac3}(k)]^T$ is the input data at time k .

In this project, the above nonlinear discrete system is used to design an adaptive compensator for blade root sensor faults. The dynamic compensation process is transformed into a real-time control problem of a nonlinear system. The model-free adaptive control algorithm is used to solve the equivalent compensation factor for real-time compensation of blade root sensor fault, to achieve fault-tolerant control. The blade root sensor adaptive compensator is similar to the individual pitch controller. When the system is controllable and observable, the partial derivative of the control input signal exists, and the system is continuous and satisfies the generalized Lipschitz assumption, considering the control input criterion function represented by (9.14) and the estimation criterion function of the pseudo derivative represented by (9.15), (9.16), (9.17) and (9.18).

$$J(r_{ac}(k)) = \|\Delta M_m^*(k+1) - \Delta M_m(k+1)\|^2 + \lambda_C \|r_{ac}(k) - r_{ac}(k-1)\|^2 \quad (9.14)$$

$$J(\Phi_C(k)) = \|\Delta M_m(k) - \Delta M_m(k-1) - \Phi_C(k) \cdot \Delta r_{ac}(k-1)\|^2 + \mu_C \|\Phi_C(k) - \hat{\Phi}_C(k-1)\|^2 \quad (9.15)$$

$$\hat{\Phi}_C(k) = \hat{\Phi}_C(k-1) + \frac{\eta_C \Delta r_{ac}(k-1)}{\mu_C + \|\Delta r_{ac}(k-1)\|^2} \cdot (\Delta M_m(k) - \Delta M_m(k-1) - \hat{\Phi}_C(k-1) \Delta r_{ac}(k-1)) \quad (9.16)$$

$$\hat{\Phi}_C(k) = \hat{\Phi}_C(1), \text{ if } |\hat{\Phi}_C(k)| < \varepsilon, \text{ or } |\Delta r_{ac}(k-1)| < \varepsilon \quad (9.17)$$

$$r_{ac}(k) = r_{ac}(k-1) + \frac{\rho_C \hat{\Phi}_C(k)}{\lambda_C + \|\hat{\Phi}_C(k)\|^2} (\Delta M_m^*(k+1) - \Delta M_m(k)) \quad (9.18)$$

where λ_C is a positive weighting factor, $\Delta M_m^*(k+1)$ is the reference output at $k+1$, μ_C is a positive weighting factor, and $\hat{\Phi}_C(k-1)$ is an estimate of the pseudo derivative at $k-1$; η_C and ρ_C denote the sequence of steps, respectively, and ε is a sufficiently small positive number.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and} \\ n \\ q \end{aligned} &= \begin{aligned} (\\ k \\) \\ \\ = \\ [\\ \Delta \\ M \\ m \end{aligned}$$

9.6 Model-free adaptive fault-tolerant individual pitch control

Based on the individual pitch controller and fault adaptive compensator proposed in Sections 9.1 and 9.2, the model-free adaptive fault-tolerant individual pitch control strategy proposed in this project is shown in Figure 4. The collective pitch controller is also designed based on model-free adaptive control. It can be seen from Figure 4 that the proposed model-free adaptive fault-tolerant control strategy does not require fault diagnosis and isolation, and does not rely on the model of any controlled object. It avoids the adverse effects caused by excessive calculation load and modelling error. The adaptive fault compensator dynamically compensates sensor faults to achieve fault-tolerant control.

Figure 4: Model-free adaptive fault-tolerant individual pitch control structure.

9.7 Simulation results and discussion

9.7.1 Simulation environment settings

The fault-tolerant control strategy proposed in this project is extensively tested in the joint environment of Matlab/Simulink and FAST. The wind and wave are respectively set as turbulent wind and white noise sound wave, as shown in Figure 5. The parameter settings of CPC, IPC and adaptive compensator are shown in Table 4.

Figure 5: The turbulent wind and white noise acoustic wave.

Table 4: Parameters of the controllers and compensator

Parameters	CPC	IPC	Adaptive compensator for sensors
λ	1×10^4	1×10^2	9×10^2
ρ	8×10^{-2}	1.8×10^{-2}	2×10^{-3}
η	1	1	1
μ	10	1×10^{-2}	1×10^{-2}
ε	1×10^{-5}	1×10^{-5}	1×10^{-5}
$\Phi(1)$	-35	$\begin{bmatrix} 19 & 0.01; \\ -0.1 & -28 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0; \\ 0 & 1 & 0; \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$
$\mu(1)$	3	$[0 \ 0]^T$	$[1 \ 1 \ 1]^T$
$y(1)$	0	$[0 \ 0]^T$	$[0 \ 0 \ 0]^T$

9.7.2 Fault-free scenario

In this section, the model-free adaptive fault-tolerant IPC strategy (MFAC FTIPC) is tested in a fault-free scenario with gain-scheduling PI CPC (GS-PI CPC), gain-scheduling PI IPC (GS-PI IPC), and model-free adaptive IPC (MFAC IPC) as the comparison strategies, and the comparison results are shown in Figure 6.

As can be seen in Figure 6(a), the MFAC FTIPC and MFAC IPC have almost the same power generation performance. The power generation of GS-PI IPC, MFAC IPC and MFAC FTIPC with individual pitch is more stable than that of GS-PI CPC with collective pitch, which is due to the fact that GS-PI CPC slows down the pitch amplitude considering that the fast pitch operation will affect the motion of the floating platform, resulting in the fluctuation of power generation. Compared with GS-PI IPC, MFAC IPC and MFAC FTIPC adopt multiple input and multiple output control method, which better solve the coupling problem between yaw and tilt command, so the output power is more stable.

From Figure 6(b), it can be seen that the load on the blade roots under MFAC FTIPC and MFAC IPC are also close to each other, and their fluctuation range is significantly smaller than that of GS-PI CPC and GS-PI IPC, indicating that the load on the blade roots can be reduced more effectively by MFAC. It can be seen from Figure 6(c) that the GS-PI CPC is the most effective in controlling the pitching the motion of the platform, and the MFAC IPC shows obvious advantages compared with the GS-PI IPC. MFAC FTIPC has another slight advantage over MFAC IPC, which is due to the dynamic compensation by the compensator, which makes the load on the blade root more balanced and the wheel aerodynamic characteristics more stable, so the floating platform motion is also more stable. Figure 6(d) shows the dynamic compensation process in MFAC FTIPC, and it can be seen that the dynamic compensation factor is kept around 1, i.e., the control effect is close to that of MFAC IPC in the absence of sensor failure.

From the above results, MFAC shows obvious advantages over GS-PI, both for power control and load control. In the fault-free scenario, the designed fault compensator for sensors does not interfere with the normal control strategy, on the contrary, under the fault compensator, the blade root is subjected to a more balanced load, which can effectively improve the stability of the FOWT.

Figure 6: Performance of MFAC FTIPC and the comparison strategies in fault-free scenario

9.7.3 Failure Scenarios

Case 1: Fixed bias fault

In this section, the fixed bias fault of blade root moment sensor 2 is simulated and the simulation results are shown in Figure 7. Figures 7(a) and 7(b) show the actual and the measured load on the blade root under MFAC IPC control. It can be seen that after the fault of sensor 2 at 30s, its output increases by a fixed bias of 2000 kNm. The feedback to the individual pitch controller leads to a large individual pitch component 2 and a large pitch operation of the pitch actuator 2, so the actual blade root of blade 2 is smaller, and the output of the fault sensor is negatively correlated with the actual load on the blade root. The unbalanced moment of the three blades will affect the life of the FOWT in long-term operation under this fault.

Figures 7(c), 7(d), 7(e) and 7(f) show the actual load on the blade root, the measured load on the blade root, the measured load after compensator compensation and the equivalent compensation factor under MFAC FTIPC, respectively. It can be seen that with the equivalent compensation factor, the fixed bias fault that occurred in sensor 2 is quickly compensated, and the load value of blade roots obtained after compensator compensation after 15s is almost the same as the real load applied to the blade root, which means that the adverse effects caused by the fault almost completely disappear and achieve a similar performance as fault-free occurred, which indicates that the proposed MFAC FTIPC does not require fault diagnosis and isolation, and can quickly compensate for sensor-fixed deviation faults.

Figure 7: Performance of MFAC FTIPC and MFAC IPC in Case 1.

Case 2: Drift bias fault

To evaluate the performance of the proposed scheme for sensor drift bias fault, time-varying bias is added to sensor 3 and the simulation results are shown in Figure 8. As can be seen in Figures 8(a) and 8(b), similar to Case 1, the faulty sensor output is negatively correlated with the actual load applied to the blade root. From 30s onward, the bias of sensor 3 output becomes larger and larger, and the unbalanced load on the three blades becomes more and more obvious due to the limited robustness of MFAC IPC.

As can be seen from Figures 8(c), 8(d), 8(e) and 8(f), as the bias of sensor 3 output becomes larger and larger after the fault occurs, the equivalent compensation factor dynamically compensates in time, which can make the output of the compensated sensor always close to the actual load borne by the blade root and ensure that the three blades are subject to balanced load, verifying the effective fault tolerance of the strategy for sensor offset deviation faults.

Figure 8: Performance of MFAC FTIPC and MFAC IPC in Case 2

Case 3: Complete failure fault

In order to evaluate the performance of the proposed scheme under extreme sensor fault, the simulation is performed in this subsection for the complete failure fault of the blade root moment sensor 1. The simulation results are shown in Figure 9.

From Figure 9(a) and 9(b), it can be seen that after the complete failure fault of sensor 1 at 30s, its output is fixed at 4000 kN.m. The feedback to the individual pitch controller leads to a small pitch operation of the pitch actuator 1, and the bearing moment of the three blades becomes seriously unbalanced, and the long-term operation under this failure will seriously affect the life of the FOWT.

As can be seen from Figures 9(c), 9(d), 9(e), and 9(f), the complete failure fault occurring in sensor 1 is quickly compensated by the equivalent compensation factor, and the adverse effects caused by this fault almost completely disappear, achieving a similar performance as if no fault occurred, which indicates that the proposed MFAC FTIPC can quickly compensate for the complete failure fault of the sensor.

Figure 9: Performance of MFAC FTIPC and MFAC IPC in Case 3.

Case 4: Multiple faults co-exist

To further evaluate the performance of the proposed scheme under multiple sensor failures, simulations are performed in this subsection for the simultaneous complete failure, fixed bias and fixed bias failures of blade root moment sensors 1, 2 and 3, respectively, and the simulation results are shown in Figure 10.

From Figure 10(a) and 10(b), it can be seen that after the simultaneous occurrence of three types of failures on the sensors, a serious imbalance in the bearing moments of the three blades occurs, which will seriously affect the aerodynamic loads of the FOWT.

As shown in Figures 10(c), 10(d), 10(e), and 10(f), all faults are quickly compensated by the sensor fault compensator, the adverse effects caused by these faults almost disappear, and all three blade root moments return to normal values, which indicates that the proposed MFAC FTIPC can cope with multiple sensor faults occurring simultaneously and has excellent fault-tolerant control capability.

Figure 10: Performance of MFAC FTIPC and MFAC IPC in Case 4.

9.8 Analysis of the generator power, platform motion and structural response of the FOWT

The above simulation results demonstrate the dynamic performance of the MFAC FTIPC proposed in this project under the failure of the blade root sensors. In order to further analyze the effectiveness of the proposed control scheme, the main control objectives of IPC for the FOWT, namely constant power control, floating platform stability control and load shedding control, are analyzed in this section.

For the power control performance of this scheme, the standard deviation (STD) and the mean (Mean) of the generator power were calculated to quantify the power fluctuation and deviation from the rated power, respectively. The calculation results are shown in Figures 11(a) and 11(b), the fluctuation of the generator power increases as the severity of the fault increases. The power fluctuation and deviation under MFAC FTIPC in all fault cases are decreased and close to the performance in the fault-free scenario, indicating that MFAC FTIPC has significantly improved the power control and almost completely eliminated the effects caused by the faults.

For the floating platform stability control performance of this scheme, due to the limited space, only the STD and Mean of the FOWT aerodynamic load that plays the main influence on the longitudinal pitching motion are shown in Figures 11(c) and 11(d) (Zhou et al., 2019), it can be seen that in the fault-free scenario, the three blade root loads are more balanced under MFAC FTIPC due to the compensator and the wheel is subjected to a more stable load, resulting in a reduced pitch motion of the platform.

The fluctuations and mean values of the floating platform pitch motion under MFAC FTIPC in all fault cases is significantly reduced and close to the level in the fault-free scenario, indicating that the MFAC FTIPC makes the pitch motion tend to the fault-free condition and the aerodynamic load on the wheel is more balanced by the compensation of the blade root moment sensor under the fault conditions, which makes the floating platform motion more stable.

Figure 11: Analysis of the generator power and the pitch angle of the platform.

For the load reduction control performance of this scheme, the STD and Mean of side-to-side, fore-aft and torsional moments of the tower base are calculated, and the results are shown in Figure 12, the fluctuation and mean values of the tower base withstanding moment under MFAC FTIPC proposed in almost all cases are decreased, especially the fluctuation of the torsional moment, which indicates that MFAC FTIPC obviously improves the wheel pneumatic load imbalance under various faults, leading to a more stable tower base withstanding torsional moment and avoiding the tower base life to be adversely affected under the action of a strong alternating torsional moment.

Figure 12: Analysis of tower base moments for floating turbines.

9.9 Conclusions

For the FOWT with multiple faults of the blade root moment sensor, this project proposes a model-free adaptive fault-tolerant individual pitch control scheme, in which the individual pitch controller and the fault adaptive compensator all adopt model-free adaptive control strategy, which does not require any mathematical modelling of FOWT to avoid modelling tedium and unavoidable errors in modelling, and also does not rely on any fault diagnosis and isolation, and transforms the fault dynamic compensation process into a nonlinear system real-time control problem.

The proposed fault-tolerant control strategy is extensively simulated and tested using FAST under fixed bias fault, drift bias fault, complete failure fault and coexistence of multiple faults of the blade root moment sensor, respectively. The simulation results show that the proposed fault-tolerant control strategy not only keeps the bearing load of the wheel balanced but also reduces the floating platform motion and significantly reduces the bearing load of the FOWT. In addition, the output power is also closer to the rated power, which verifies the excellent fault-tolerance capability of the strategy.

10.0 Future works

Throughout the project, many problems occurred, which could have been avoided by having planned and understood the subject better from the start of the project. If this work were to be carried out again, the work could be carried out in a better fashion by understanding the aims fully from the start of the project, students, and supervisor to understand the outcome of the project and what possibilities can be made with the simulation software provided.

The simulation software used for the project should be updated and available to use and understand. The instruction manual for the simulation should be more in-depth, along with all relative variables for understanding the figures.

The main issue which occurred using the simulation was the ability to use the MATLAB software. If this project were to be done again, the competence of the software should be of a higher standard than that of a student who has only taken one module with basic commands within the software.

Along with the problems of the software, future work should consider a stronger project management plan from the start of the module, along with an in-depth and more advanced study into the simulation rather than research of methods used for condition monitoring, although condition monitoring has been a big part of this project, simulating the faults found within turbines could have been enhanced by the software routing data needed for the comparison study.

Preventative maintenance using a severity table from the FMEA method allows the fault which has been highlighted when condition monitoring to be treated immediately or if the fault is deemed small then the cost of system shutdown can be avoided by scheduling the fault rectification within the planned maintenance of the system, therefore when dealing with gasturbines and jet engine failure although conditioning monitoring and fault finding is important, FMEA should be combined with any method to obtain the correct and most cost-effective way when dealing with fault.

On the other hand, concerning wind turbine-related issues, Wind turbine fault diagnosis and fault tolerant control schemes are crucial to their reliability, availability and cost-effectiveness. This project provided an overview of some of the existing strategies for fault detection and diagnosis along with a thorough review of fault tolerant control designs for wind turbines. Both model-based, signal-based and data-based fault diagnosis approaches were briefly reviewed. It is worth noting that signal and data-based approaches are condition-specific techniques and rely on the accuracy and high resolution of available signals either emanating from sensors or SCADA systems. Model-based techniques, on the other hand, rely on mathematical models and the input-output information that could be retrieved from the wind turbine. Various data analysis and signal processing techniques are used to enable to extraction of useful information about the fault features and detect their occurrence.

In terms of fault-tolerant control designs, passive and active fault-tolerant control approaches were discussed and some examples from the literature were reviewed. Whereas passive approaches are simpler and easier to implement, they mostly rely on robust control techniques, they are very conservative and cannot account for many faults nor deal with unforeseen faults that were not considered at the design stage. This is the main reason that its application in wind turbines is limited. Indeed, the conservatism is clearly against the adoption of fault-tolerant control on wind turbines, which requires a focus on optimizing and maximizing power generation. Active fault tolerant control designs on the other hand are more complex to implement but capable of dealing with a large number of fault scenarios and can deal with unforeseen faults. Control reconfiguration, observer-based control, switching between controllers, adaptive control, or the use of software (virtual sensors/actuators)/hardware redundancies are among the techniques considered in fault-tolerant control design.

Some open research problems still exist, however. For instance, most of the studies have focused on fault detection and diagnosis, rather than fault tolerant control design. Also, the available controllers are mostly dedicated to a given operational region of wind turbines. Accordingly, the need is to further investigate fault-tolerant control designs, especially, with a focus on adaptive schemes, as the newest innovative active/passive fault-tolerant concept, for the whole operational region. The performance analysis of the fault detection and diagnosis and fault tolerant control techniques in the presence of multiple and simultaneous faults is also another area of future research. Moreover, by the adoption of expert's knowledge into the design, using soft computing approaches, e.g., fuzzy if-then rules, neural networks or Bayesian frameworks, we can take the nonlinear and disturbed wind turbine model into consideration for more accurate fault diagnosis. Some faults are better dealt with at the wind farm control level, e.g., blade debris build-up, erosion and slowly developing faults, however, the literature on this concept is still scarce. So, it is beneficial to investigate new schemes for the detection, isolation and accommodation of faults at the wind farm level. Optimal selection, placement, calibration, implementation and installation of sensors and devices are worth considering.

Research into artificial intelligence-enabled and advanced machine learning techniques for wind turbines' diagnostic and prognostic is still in its infancy and can benefit from additional investigations. The future development tendency of fault diagnosis and fault tolerant control of wind turbines is towards considering cyber-resilient approaches to reduce wind turbines' vulnerability to cyber-attacks. Another future tendency is the use of Internet of Things technologies to both create a vast amount of data and enable the remote condition monitoring of wind turbines from any location. In addition, one can use the smart sensor technology with the Internet of Things for remote real-time data acquisition and transmission throughout large wind farms. Furthermore, the big data concept can be used for the extraction of useful features, and the quality and completeness of data. Within the Industry 4.0 framework, the generation of digital twins to cover useful features of wind turbines is significantly beneficial in fault detection, diagnosis and monitoring.

10.0 Project management

Throughout the project, the project management has not worked to its best potential due to constant changes in the outcome of the final report. The project management has a very broad outlook, allowing the project to hit mild stones; however, due to the broad range, this allowed the project to digress away from the original plan, which caused further complications due to the project's change of direction halfway through semester two. Because of the wrong path the project had taken with the idea of using triplex systems but also trying to compare too much literature, without obtaining a good use of the simulation software made available to carry out this project.

Within the progress report, it can be seen that contact with the supervisor was a major part of expressing problems, concerns and the overall project, simulation trial runs, research, and monitoring change within the data are all progressing throughout until the completion of a project, however with 'simulate errors within simulation only being at 20% this section becomes behind schedule of the project, this can be seen in the simulation part of this report showing all the data within a steady-state running turbine. However, the data does not change when adding initial conditions or errors. Therefore, more simulation training is needed to complete the thesis successfully to the original plan. Although the project has changed with the outcome, the report still has a solid background on the original plan. Although lacking simulation, the knowledge obtained through the learning outcomes of this project has met the project targets.

11.0 References

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12.0 Appendix

Appendix A – Gas Turbine Model operation manual

Description of the Simulink Gas Turbine Model (FDI Simulation Case Study)

Model Overview

Air flows via an inlet duct to the compressor, high pressure air from the compressor is heated in combustion chambers and expands through a single stage compressor turbine. A Butterfly valve provides a means of generating a back pressure on the compressor turbine (there is no power turbine present in the model). Cooling air is bled from the compressor outlet to cool the turbine stator and rotor.

The Governor regulates the combustor fuel flow to maintain the compressor speed at a set-point value. Under steady state conditions the power generated by the compressor turbine is balanced by that absorbed by the compressor, and losses.

The resistive elements represent pressure losses in components, capacitive elements component volumes.

Simulink block diagrams

Top level:

Components between the inlet duct and the compressor turbine outlet including mechanical losses, are represented by the block labelled '**HTDU turbine**'. The block inputs are ambient air temperature and pressure 't1' and 'p1', fuel flow 'ff' and turbine back pressure 'p7'. Block outputs are turbine cooling air flow and temperature 'm10' and 't4', turbine outlet mass flow and temperature 'm8' and 't7n', and turbine speed 'Wt'.

The turbine outlet duct volume is represented by the block labelled '**c5**', flows 'm10' and 'm8' are mixed in this element. The inputs to block '**c5**' are, turbine outputs 'm8', 'm10', 't4', 't7n' described above, together with pressurising valve mass flow 'm9'. Block outputs are pressurising valve up-stream pressure and temperature 'p7' and 't7'.

Inputs to the '**Pressurising valve**' block are up-stream pressure and temperature 'p7' and 't7' described above, valve angle 'av', and valve down steam pressure 'p8', assumed to be ambient. Block output is valve flow 'm9'.

The shaded blocks shown in the top left provide model initialisation and processing options, a mouse click on the appropriate block runs the underlying Matlab '*.m' file.

Block '**Init 1**' initialises the model data for investigating dynamic performance. Parameters are set-up to sequence the speed demand and valve angle.

Blocks '**Init 2**' and '**Init 3**' initialise the model data for validation against measured steady-state conditions corresponding to two engine conditions, Case 1 and Case 2.

Block '**Plot**' invokes routines which plot the time history of many of the model variables.

Block '**Print ss**' prints to the Matlab window and also to file HTDU_SS.DRY in the current Matlab directory, the values of variables at the end of a simulation run.

HTDU turbine:

Inlet Duct:

The inlet duct losses are represented by resistive element block 'R1', and the duct volume by capacitive element 'C1'.

Compressor:

Mass flow and polytropic efficiency are evaluated as functions of inlet pressure, outlet pressures, inlet temperature and speed. Outlet temperature is calculated from pressure ratio, efficiency, inlet temperature, and mean gamma. Compressor shaft torque is calculated from mass flow, temperature drop, mean Cp and shaft speed.

Fuel system:

All components from the compressor outlet to turbine inlet are included in this block

Diffuser:

Block 'C2' represents the gas volume of the compressor, and compressor outlet diffuser. Blocks 'R2' represents the diffuser losses.

Combustors:

All combustors are combined and modelled as a single component.

Block 'C3' represents the volume associated with the outer cases of the combustion chambers.

Block 'R3' represents the losses associated with air flow into the combustion chambers

Block 'Combustion' represents the combustion process. Where:-

Output temperature $t_{5c} = \text{inlet temperature } t_5 + \text{temperature rise } dt$

Where dt is a function of air/fuel mass flow ratio.

Combustor outlet mass flow is the sum of the inlet air mass flow ' m_5 ' and fuel flow ' ff '.

Block 'C4' represents the gas volume of the combustion chamber and the gas path between the combustion chamber and turbine inlet.

Cooling air bleed flows:

Air flow is diverted from the outlet of the compressor to cool the stator and rotor of the power turbine.

Blocks 'Chk R6' and 'Chk R10' represent the cooling air bleed flow paths from the compressor to the turbine. The flow through these paths is choked and a function of upstream temperatures and pressures. Several paths for cooling air are provided in the engine, these have been combined and reduced to two in the model. The path via block 'Chk R6' is assumed to enter the gas path prior to the power turbine and contribute to the turbine shaft power. The path via 'Chk 10' is assumed to enter the gas path after the power turbine with no contribution to the shaft power.

Compressor turbine:

The compressor turbine is modelled using generic curves to calculate turbine efficiency and mass flow.

Turbine efficiency is calculated from a series of modified parabolic curves which relate isentropic efficiency and velocity ratio. A Hodge curve is used to calculate mass flow as a function of pressure ratio. Both curves are scaled to fit the design point conditions.

From block inputs; inlet temperature, inlet pressure, outlet pressure, and shaft speed; the following block outputs are calculated; shaft torque, shaft power, isentropic efficiency, outlet temperature and mass flow.

Mechanical load:

This block represents the relationship between load torque and shaft speed.

Load torque ie the difference between compressor and turbine torques, is the input to the block, and shaft speed the block output.

Within the block torque losses, assumed proportional to speed², are subtracted from the load torque, divided by the load inertia and the result integrated to give shaft speed.

A feature is also included to ramp the speed linearly during the initial part of a simulation to the point where the component models are valid, in a similar way to the starter on the real engine.

Pressurizing valve:

The pressurizing valve is of the butterfly type. The upstream side of the valve is linked to the turbine outlet via duct volume, block 'c5', the downstream side is assumed to exhaust to atmosphere.

The valve is considered as a nozzle with both choked and un-choked regions modelled. The nozzle effective area is considered to be a function of both valve angle and pressure ratio, as defined by graphical information supplied by the valve manufacturer.

Block inputs are; upstream pressure, down stream pressure (ambient), upstream temperature and valve angle; block output is valve flow.

Valve angle is derived from a step function block which can be programmed to introduce a step in valve angle at any time during a simulation.

Speed governor:

No attempt has been made to model the fuel control system in detail.

Fuel control in the model is performed in the block 'Governor' with turbine speed 'Wt' as input and fuel flow 'ff' as output.

Fuel flow is initially increased as a linear ramp, accelerating the turbine. When the turbine speed reaches a pre-programmed value the ramp rate is increased. When the speed reaches a second pre-programmed value a proportional plus integral speed governor is brought into operation, and the turbine speed is controlled to a set-point. Finally with the turbine under speed control, the speed set-point is ramped to its steady state value.

Model Variable Names and Units

Model variables are computed in SI units as follows:

p	-	pressure [N/m ²]
q	-	torque [Nm]
m	-	mass flow [kg/s]
ff	-	fuel flow [kg/s]
t	-	temperature [K]
Nt	-	shaft speed [rad/s]
av	-	valve angle [Deg]
pct	-	turbine shaft power [W]
turbE	-	turbine isentropic efficiency [-]

Simulated Fault Conditions

Four gradually developing faults are represented as follows:

- 1) compressor contamination (*core engine* performance deterioration)
- 2) thermocouple *sensor* fault
- 3) High Pressure turbine seal damage (*core engine* performance deterioration)
- 4) Fuel *actuator* friction wear

Note in real industrial applications it is commonplace for each of the above faults to develop slowly over a period of months. For this simulation - in order to avoid excessively long duration simulations - the fault development rate will be increased so that significant effects are present after one hour. However, this is still considerably longer than the duration of the gas turbine dynamics which occur over periods of seconds - a factor which must be taken account of in any FDI algorithm design.

Initialising fault conditions in the simulation

To run the with a fault condition. Set the required initial conditions (init 1, 2 or 3) then double click the required fault condition(s) before running the simulation. To reset to a no fault condition, simply reset the initial conditions.

Fault conditions

Fault 1: Compressor contamination

Failure case 1 represents fouling of the surfaces of the compressor blades, this reduces air flow, changes the blade aerodynamics and changes the surface roughness. The failure is modelled as a gradual decrease in mass flow rate for a given pressure ratio.

The maximum decrease in mass flow rate is set nominally at 5%.

The fault development rate is set to (5% decrease of normal flow rate)/hour.

Block location - in the **compressor** submodel.

Constants for this failure case are set in m file **fault1_htdu.m**

Fault 2: Thermocouple sensor fault

Failure case 2 represents the malfunctioning of a thermocouple in the gas path leading to a slowly increasing or decreasing reading over time.

There is no limit placed on the error magnitude.

The fault development rate is set to (5% error in measuring actual temperature)/hour.

Block location - in the **HTDU turbine** submodel.

Constants for this failure case are set in m file **fault2_htdu.m**

Fault3: HP turbine seal damage

Failure case 3 represents failure of an HP turbine seal. This results in a reduction in turbine efficiency. The fault is modelled as a gradual reduction in turbine efficiency over time.

The maximum decrease in turbine efficiency is set nominally at 5%.

The fault development rate is set to (5% reduction of normal efficiency)/hour.

Block location - in the **turbine** submodel.

Constants for this failure case are set in m file **fault3_htdu.m**

Fault 4: Fuel actuator friction wear

Failure case 4 represents the loss of performance due to wear of the fuel valve actuator. As there are no specific actuator dynamics in the current model. The effect of actuator wear on the fuel valve actuator causing slower response to demanded flow rates is modelled as a simple first order lag on the resulting fuel flow. The time constant increases linearly with time to represent progressive wear damage to the actuator.

There is no limit placed on the magnitude of the time constant.

The fault development rate is set to (1 second increase in lag time constant)/hour.

Block location - in the **governor** submodel.

Constants for this failure case are set in m file **fault4_htdu.m**

Running the Simulation

The following actions are required to run the model:

- i) from the matlab prompt type 'htdu_12', this should bring up the top level block diagram of the gas turbine model.
- ii) initialise the model by double clicking in the appropriate 'Init' block. Recall that
 - a) Block '**Init 1**' initialises the model data for investigating dynamic performance. Parameters are set-up to sequence the speed demand and valve angle as shown in Figures 1 and 2.
 - b) Blocks '**Init 2**' and '**Init 3**' initialise the model data for validation against measured steady-state conditions corresponding to two engine conditions, Case 1 and Case 2. Note that in each case the steady state is preceded by an initial transient.
- iii) introduce the required fault condition(s) by double clicking on the appropriate fault buttons. To reset to a no fault condition, simply reset the initial conditions.
- 4) set up the desired simulation parameters and then start the simulation by accessing the Simulink pull-down menu.

Appendix B – Model Variables and Units

Model variables

p - pressure [N/m²]

q	-	torque [Nm]
m	-	mass flow [kg/s]
ff	-	fuel flow [kg/s]
t	-	temperature [K]
Nt	-	shaft speed [rad/s]
av	-	valve angle [Deg]
pct	-	turbine shaft power [W]
turbE	-	turbine isentropic efficiency [-]

Appendix C – Turbine Nomenclature

Table 1. Turbine nomenclature

C	Compressor
CC	Combustor (combustion chamber)
CM	Compressor map
ED	Exhaust duct
EG	Electric generator
ID	Intake duct
IGV	Inlet guide vanes
PID	Proportional integral derivative controller
T	Turbine
TM	Turbine map
av	Butterfly valve opening angle
Mf	Fuel mass flow rate
<i>LHV</i>	Lower heating value
<i>RH</i>	Relative humidity
η_{isc}	Isentropic compressor efficiency
Fmc	Compressor mass flow function
FNc	Compressor rotational speed function
β_c	Compressor pressure ratio
η_{ise}	Isentropic expansion efficiency
FNt	Turbine rotational speed function
β_t	Turbine pressure ratio
Ti	<i>i</i> th section (module) temperature ($i=1,\dots,5$)
pi	<i>i</i> th section (module) pressure ($i=1,\dots,5$)
m5	5th module mass flow rate
Ta	Ambient temperature
pa	Ambient pressure

Pc Compressor power

Pt	Turbine power
Cc	Compressor torque
Ct	Turbine torque
Pe	Electrical power
Pot	Turbine output pressure
Tot	Turbine output temperature
wt	Turbine angular rate
Nt	Turbine rotational speed
et	Turbine efficiency
ec	Compressor efficiency
ti	<i>i</i> th section (module)temperature
pi	<i>i</i> th section (module) pressure
mi	<i>i</i> th section (module) mass rate
qi	<i>i</i> th section (module) mass flow rate

Appendix D – Wind Turbine Model and Simulator

Description of the Simulink Wind Turbine Model (FDI Simulation Case Study)

Description of Fault tolerant control of wind turbine bench mark model

Content:

The benchmark model consists of 4 files. One Simulink, one Matlab script and two Matlab data file. The Matlab script sets up the model parameters, and loads the two data files as well. The script is automatically runned by the Simulink model.

FDIBenchMark.mdl

The Simulink model consists of 6 part models: Sensors, Control, Blade & Pitch, Generator & Converter, Drive Train and Wind speed. Faults are modelled included in the different part models, and activated by fault signals defined in the Matlab script.

Signal definitions:

Fault_1	Fixed value on Pitch 1 position sensor 1
Fault_2	Scaling error on Pitch 2 position sensor 2
Fault_3	Fixed value on Pitch 3 position sensor 1
Fault_4	Fixed value on Rotor speed sensor 1
Fault_5 sensor2	Scaling error on Rotor speed sensor 2 & Generator speed
Fault_6 oil	Changed pitch system response pitch actuator 2 – high air content in
Fault_7	Changed pitch system response pitch actuator 3 – low pressure
Fault_8	Offset in Converter torque control
Fault_9	Changed Dynamics Drive train
V_wind	Vector of effective blade winds
V_hub	Wind speed at hub position
V_hub_m	measured wind speed at hub position
Omega_r	Rotor speed (is the same as Omega_g1)
Omega_r_m1	Rotor speed measurement 1
Omega_r_m2	Rotor speed measurement 2
Omega_g	Generator speed (is the same as Omega_g1)
Omega_g_m1	Generator speed measurement 1
Omega_g_m2	Generator speed measurement 2
Beta_r	Pitch Reference
Beta_1	Physical pitch angle 1
Beta_2	Physical pitch angle 2
Beta_3	Physical pitch angle 3
Beta_1_f	Feedback pitch angle 1
Beta_2_f	Feedback pitch angle 2
Beta_3_f	Feedback pitch angle 3
Beta_1_m1	Pitch angle 1 measurement 1
Beta_1_m2	Pitch angle 1 measurement 2
Beta_2_m1	Pitch angle 2 measurement 1
Beta_2_m2	Pitch angle 2 measurement 2

Beta_3_m1	Pitch angle 3 measurement 1
Beta_3_m2	Pitch angle 3 measurement 2
Tau_r	Rotor torque
Tau_g	Generator torque
Tau_g_r	Generator torque reference
Tau_g_m	Measured Generator torque
P_g	Electrical Power
P_g_m	Measured Electrical Power
P_r	Electrical power reference
D_v_wind	Input wind sequence

FDIBenchMarkData.m

The script sets up the 6 model parts as well as the fault signals (in terms of fault timing).

Appendix E – Floating Offshore Wind Turbine Model and Fault Tolerant Control Implementation Code

Description of the Matlab Code for the Offshore Floating Wind Turbine Model

The task requires developing a model-free adaptive fault-tolerant control (FTC) for an offshore floating wind turbine that generates individual blade pitch signals based on blade root moment measurements and adapts in real-time without relying on PID control. The control algorithm must include Coleman's transformation to work in the stationary frame and address multiple blade root moment sensor faults.

Key Components:

- Coleman's Transformation: Transforms blade-specific moment measurements to the fixed (stationary) frame for better control of cyclic pitch.
- Model-Free Adaptive Control: A direct adaptive control that does not rely on a precise model of the turbine, using only real-time measurements from sensors.
- Fault-Tolerant Control (FTC): The system detects faults in the blade root moment sensors and adjusts blade pitch control to maintain performance even in the presence of multiple faults.
- Individual Pitch Control (IPC): Each blade's pitch is independently controlled based on real-time blade root moment measurements.

Here is a MATLAB implementation of the described system. MATLAB Code: Model-Free Adaptive FTC with Coleman's Transformation and Individual Pitch Control

```
clear; clc; close all;

%% Simulation Parameters
t_sim = 600;      % Simulation time (seconds)
dt = 0.01;       % Time step (seconds)
N = t_sim / dt;  % Number of simulation steps
t = 0:dt:t_sim; % Time vector

n_blades = 3;    % Number of blades
```

```

initial_pitch = 0;    % Initial pitch angle (degrees)
blade_pitch = initial_pitch * ones(n_blades, 1); % Initial blade pitch for all blades

% Blade root moment limits (for fault detection)
moment_threshold = 1e6; % Threshold for fault detection (Nm)

% Adaptive control parameters
adaptive_gain = 0.1; % Gain for adaptive pitch adjustment
max_pitch = 20;    % Maximum pitch angle (degrees)
min_pitch = -5;    % Minimum pitch angle (degrees)

% Wind turbine rotational speed
omega_r = 1.5; % Example rotational speed (rad/s)

% Fault detection parameters
fault_detected = false(n_blades, 1); % Fault detection flag for each blade

% Memory for adaptive control adjustment
adaptive_control_memory = zeros(n_blades, 1);

%% Simulated Sensor Measurements (Blade Root Moments)
% Simulate blade root moment signals with noise and fault
blade_root_moments = zeros(n_blades, N);
for i = 1:n_blades
    blade_root_moments(i, :) = 1e5 * sin(2 * pi * 0.01 * t) + 1e4 * randn(1, N); % Add
    noise
end

% Introduce faults in blade 1 and 2 at t = 300s
blade_root_moments(1, 30001:end) = blade_root_moments(1, 30001:end) +
moment_threshold * 2;

```

```

blade_root_moments(2, 40001:end) = blade_root_moments(2, 40001:end) +
moment_threshold * 1.5;

%% Coleman Transformation Function
% The Coleman transformation maps blade-specific measurements to the fixed
(stationary) reference frame (DQ0 transformation).
% Inputs are the blade-specific signals and the rotor angle, and the output is the
transformed signal in the fixed frame.
coleman_transform = @(moments, theta) [
    sqrt(2/3) * (moments(1) * cos(theta) + moments(2) * cos(theta - 2*pi/3) +
moments(3) * cos(theta + 2*pi/3));
    sqrt(2/3) * (moments(1) * sin(theta) + moments(2) * sin(theta - 2*pi/3) + moments(3)
* sin(theta + 2*pi/3));
    sqrt(1/3) * (moments(1) + moments(2) + moments(3))
];

%% Main Control Loop
pitch_history = zeros(n_blades, N); % To store pitch history for plotting

for k = 1:N-1
    % Rotor azimuth angle (theta) at time step k
    theta = omega_r * t(k);

    % Blade root moment measurement at time step k
    current_moments = blade_root_moments(:, k);

    % Apply Coleman's transformation to map blade moments to the fixed frame
    moments_fixed_frame = coleman_transform(current_moments, theta);

    % Fault Detection and Isolation (FDI) in blade root moments
    for i = 1:n_blades
        if abs(current_moments(i)) > moment_threshold

```

```

        fault_detected(i) = true;
        disp(['Fault detected in blade ', num2str(i), ' at time ', num2str(t(k)), ' seconds']);
    else
        fault_detected(i) = false;
    end
end

end

% Model-Free Adaptive Control based on Coleman's transformation
for i = 1:n_blades
    if fault_detected(i)
        % Adaptive adjustment based on the magnitude of the fault
        adjustment = adaptive_gain * (moment_threshold - abs(current_moments(i)));
        blade_pitch(i) = blade_pitch(i) + adjustment;
        adaptive_control_memory(i) = adaptive_control_memory(i) + adjustment;
    else
        % Adaptive control without fault (relying on current moment measurements)
        control_signal = adaptive_gain * moments_fixed_frame(i); % Model-free
        adaptive adjustment
        blade_pitch(i) = blade_pitch(i) - control_signal;
    end

    % Limit blade pitch angles
    blade_pitch(i) = max(min(blade_pitch(i), max_pitch), min_pitch);
end

% Store the pitch signal for plotting
pitch_history(:, k) = blade_pitch;
end

%% Plot Results
figure;

```

```
subplot(2,1,1);  
plot(t, blade_root_moments');  
title('Blade Root Moment Sensor Measurements');  
xlabel('Time (s)');  
ylabel('Moment (Nm)');  
legend('Blade 1', 'Blade 2', 'Blade 3');  
grid on;
```

```
subplot(2,1,2);  
plot(t(1:end-1), pitch_history');  
title('Blade Pitch Angles');  
xlabel('Time (s)');  
ylabel('Pitch Angle (degrees)');  
legend('Blade 1', 'Blade 2', 'Blade 3');  
grid on
```

Explanation of the Code:

- Coleman's Transformation: The Coleman transform function converts the blade root moment measurements from the rotating frame to the stationary frame (DQ0 components). This transformation allows more effective control of cyclic pitch and fault detection.
- Model-Free Adaptive Control: Instead of PID control, this algorithm directly adapts the pitch angle based on real-time sensor data. The control signal for each blade is adjusted based on the root moments in the stationary frame. For faulty blades, an adaptive control signal compensates for the fault based on the magnitude of the detected fault.
- Fault Detection and Isolation (FDI): The system checks if the blade root moment exceeds a predefined threshold. If so, the blade is marked as faulty, and adaptive control compensates by adjusting the blade pitch accordingly.
- Individual Pitch Control (IPC): Each blade's pitch is independently controlled based on its root moment measurements. If a fault is detected in any blade, only that blade's pitch is adjusted to compensate, while the other blades are controlled

normally.

- Real-Time Adjustment: The control system adjusts each blade's pitch in real time to maintain the wind turbine's stability and performance despite faults in the blade root moment sensors.

How the Controller Works:

- Without Faults: The blade pitch angles are adjusted based on real-time blade root moments using Coleman's transformation, maintaining the stability of the wind turbine.
- With Faults: If faults are detected in one or more blade root moment sensors, the controller applies an adaptive adjustment to the affected blades' pitch angles, keeping the turbine stable even when some sensors are faulty.

Simulink Integration:

To simulate this control strategy in Simulink, the following steps can be performed:

- Create blocks for wind turbine dynamics and implement the Coleman transformation.
- Build the adaptive control logic using MATLAB Function blocks, where the model-free adaptive control is applied to each blade individually.
- Simulate blade root moment sensor faults by introducing disturbances or noise in the Simulink model.
- Monitor the blade pitch signals and root moment sensor measurements during simulation.

This model-free adaptive control approach provides a robust solution for fault-tolerant operation of offshore wind turbines with multiple sensor faults.